

Bachelor's Thesis

**Macroscopic Fluctuation–Dissipation
Relations Away from Equilibrium**

**Makroskopische
Fluktuations-Dissipations-Beziehungen
außerhalb des Gleichgewichts**

prepared by

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ABSTRACT

The fluctuation–dissipation theorem (FDT) establishes a fundamental connection between a system’s equilibrium fluctuations and its linear response to external perturbations. While valid near equilibrium, it breaks down under strong perturbations, when the system’s response becomes nonlinear. In this thesis, we extend the theoretical framework describing nonequilibrium situations beyond the FDT. In particular, we investigate a system driven far away from equilibrium by a multidimensional time-dependent protocol, which generalizes earlier results on one-dimensional driving. To analyze the system’s nonequilibrium behavior, we introduce generalized connected correlation functions (GCCFs), which we identify as tensor-like quantities capturing the system’s statistical properties. Using nonlinear response relations derived within the path integral formalism, the components of the GCCFs are expressed as Volterra series expansions around the reference equilibrium state of the system. Microscopic expressions for the memory kernel components, arising from these expansions, are derived and shown to be connected through a set of component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations. These include a component-wise FDT as the lowest-order relation. From the expansions we derive a response relation that quantifies the violation of the FDT under multidimensional driving. Finally, we demonstrate that the one-dimensional driving case is naturally recovered within our framework and evaluate the FDT violation for a constant velocity protocol with two components.

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1. Introduction

Most physical systems in the real world consist of a vast number of microscopic constituents. Their macroscopic properties emerge from the collective behavior of these components, with microscopic fluctuations often playing a crucial role. One of the most fundamental everyday examples is the concept of temperature in a many-body system. On the microscopic scale, the particles are in constant motion, each with a fluctuating kinetic energy. Macroscopically on the other hand, these fluctuations average out, and the mean kinetic energy per particle becomes time-independent. Temperature is then defined as a quantity proportional to this average, making it a macroscopic property that originates from the microscopic dynamics [1].

Yet perhaps the most famous phenomenon that can be understood in this way is *Brownian motion*. Discovered by the Scottish botanist Robert Brown in 1827 [2], it describes the erratic, random motion of a colloidal particle¹, often referred to as a *Brownian particle*, when immersed in a fluid. This motion is visible under an optical microscope and arises from countless microscopic collisions of the Brownian particle with the surrounding, much faster-moving solvent molecules [4].

These examples illustrate the importance of establishing a theoretical framework to quantify microscopic behavior and connect it to observable macroscopic properties. A crucial aspect such a framework needs to consider, is the fundamental distinction between equilibrium situations, where thermodynamic observables are time-independent [5], and nonequilibrium situations, which describe most systems found in nature [6]. The latter evolve in time and are characterized by irreversible fluxes of matter and energy, as well as entropy production [6, 7]. This renders thermodynamic observables time-dependent and makes the theoretical description considerably more difficult.

Historically, the theory of Brownian motion has proven to be one of the simplest, yet most effective approaches to describe the dynamics of stochastic systems in and out of equilibrium [4]. Particularly in *Newtonian fluids* like water, where the vis-

¹Colloids are particles whose sizes typically range from about 1 nm to 1 μm [3].

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cosity is independent of the shear rate [8], Brownian motion is well studied. In such fluids, the Brownian particle relaxes on much longer time scales than the surrounding solvent bath molecules [9]. As a result, the solvent bath can be considered memoryless² or *Markovian*. The equation of motion describing the temporal evolution of the Brownian particle is the *Langevin equation*. It consists of a deterministic part, arising from friction and external forces, and a stochastic contribution that represents the random collisions with the surrounding solvent molecules [4, 5].

While such systems have been extensively studied both in equilibrium and in nonequilibrium situations, the setting of more complex solvent baths remains much less understood. Many biologically interesting fluids, such as nucleic acid condensates (e.g., DNA or RNA) [10], cytoplasm [11], or even cerebrospinal fluid³ [12], fall into this category. All of them can be classified as non-Newtonian viscoelastic fluids [10–13], characterized by long relaxation times that are of the same order of magnitude or longer than those of Brownian particles [9, 13]. This results in memory effects, where the system’s future evolution depends on its past history, not just the present state. Therefore, such baths can no longer be considered Markovian, and we require a modified *non-Markovian* description of the system [4].

Especially in nonequilibrium situations, such as when a Brownian particle immersed in a nonlinear, non-Markovian bath is strongly driven, the theoretical description becomes challenging due to the complex interactions between the driven particle and the nonlinear environment [14]. When the system is weakly driven and remains close to equilibrium, its response is linear and well described by the *fluctuation–dissipation theorem (FDT)*, which establishes a connection between the linear response to small external perturbations and the system’s internal equilibrium fluctuations [15]. However, under stronger driving, the system exhibits a nonlinear response and nonlinear fluctuations [14, 16] that are no longer captured by the FDT, requiring an extended theoretical framework. Such nonequilibrium behavior has been observed in several instances, including flow instabilities in experiments with worm-like micellar fluids [17] and shear-thinning or shear-thickening behavior in active baths [18].

Over the years, various methods have been developed to investigate nonequilibrium systems. One of the earliest was introduced in the 1950s by Ryogo Kubo, ex-

²Memoryless means that the future evolution of the system depends only on its present state, not on its past history [4, 5].

³This is the protective fluid that circulates through the brain and spinal cord, supporting the central nervous system in several ways [12].

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tending linear response theory using correlation-function expansions [19]. Following developments introduced new strategies, such as employing the maximum-entropy principle as an approximate ansatz for nonlinear response [20], or applying projection operator techniques within the Mori–Zwanzig formalism [21]. More recently, nonlinear response relations have been formulated using a stochastic path integral formalism, first introduced in Ref. [22]. They have since been applied to derive generalized Langevin equations for probes in nonlinear media [23] and to derive nonlinear Volterra series expansions for the force cumulants of a driven probe, immersed in in a fluid with nonlinear interactions [14]. Most recently, the last scenario has been extended to encompass a broader class of systems, and nonlinear-fluctuation dissipation relations for the memory kernels arising in the Volterra series expansions have been derived [16].

In this thesis, we aim to further investigate the theoretical description of strongly driven systems within the path integral formalism. In particular, we study the nonequilibrium evolution of a classical system, which we perturb away from equilibrium by applying a multidimensional, time-dependent driving protocol. This corresponds to a generalization of the formalism for one-dimensional driving developed by Juliana Caspers and Matthias Krüger in Refs. [16, 24], who demonstrated that this scenario can be formally described by a nonlinear Volterra series expansion.

The thesis is organized as follows. In Chapter 2, we introduce the core concepts and provide the necessary background. We begin with a brief review of linear response theory and describe the physical system under investigation. Next, we derive nonlinear response relations using the path integral formalism and conclude the chapter by discussing the mathematical formulation of Volterra series expansions.

Building on this, Chapter 3 investigates the nonequilibrium behavior of the system under multidimensional driving. We establish a generalized formalism demonstrating that the stochastic quantities characterizing the system can be expressed as nonlinear Volterra series expansions. From these expansions, we derive nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations for the associated memory kernels. Finally, we use these results to formulate a response relation that provides a measure for the violation of the FDT.

In Chapter 4, we apply the derived formalism to two special cases. First, we demonstrate that the one-dimensional driving scenario is naturally recovered from the generalized framework. Second, we evaluate the violation of the FDT for a two-component constant velocity protocol.

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Chapter 5 concludes the thesis by summarizing the developed formalism and discussing the obtained physical results. In addition, we provide possible directions for future research, including further generalizations and opportunities for simulations and experimental validation.

2. Background

2.1. Linear Response Theory

When applying a small perturbation to a system in equilibrium, its response is linear in the perturbation. This effect is described by the well-established framework of linear response theory, which quantifies the response in terms of time-correlation functions evaluated within the equilibrium ensemble [25].

We consider a system weakly coupled to a time-dependent external field $\mathcal{F}(t)$, which represents the applied perturbation. The Hamiltonian of the perturbed system reads

$$H = H_0 + H_1(t), \quad (2.1)$$

where H_0 denotes the equilibrium part of the energy and $H_1(t) = -A\mathcal{F}(t)$ is the time-dependent perturbation Hamiltonian. The external field $\mathcal{F}(t)$ is chosen to couple linearly to an arbitrary phase-space observable $A = A(q, p)$, where q and p denote the coordinates and momenta of all particles in the system. Hence, $\mathcal{F}(t)$ is the observable conjugate to A . Formally, the system can be treated by solving the Liouville equation [25]

$$\frac{\partial f(t)}{\partial t} = -i\mathcal{L}f(t) = -i\mathcal{L}_0f(t) - \{A, f(t)\}\mathcal{F}(t) \quad (2.2)$$

to obtain the phase-space probability density $f(t) \equiv f(q, p; t)$ of the perturbed system. Solving Eq. (2.2) thus provides a phase-space description that encompasses all degrees of freedom of the particles in the system. Here, $\mathcal{L}(\cdot) \equiv i\{H, \cdot\}$ and $\mathcal{L}_0(\cdot) \equiv i\{H_0, \cdot\}$ denote the Liouville operators corresponding to the total and equilibrium Hamiltonian, respectively [25]. They are expressed in terms of the Poisson brackets $\{\cdot, \cdot\}$ from classical Hamiltonian mechanics. As a boundary condition, we assume the system was in equilibrium in the infinite past, $t_0 \rightarrow -\infty$, so that $f(t_0) = f_{\text{eq}}$ is the Boltzmann distribution. Due to considering only small perturbations (i.e. weak

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external fields), we decompose the distribution function into an equilibrium part f_{eq} and a time-dependent correction $\Delta f(t)$ [25],

$$f(t) = f_{\text{eq}} + \Delta f(t). \quad (2.3)$$

Evaluating Eq. (2.2) for this decomposed distribution function yields the linearized Liouville equation

$$\frac{\partial \Delta f(t)}{\partial t} = -i\mathcal{L}_0 \Delta f(t) - \{A, f_{\text{eq}}\} \mathcal{F}(t). \quad (2.4)$$

The formal solution of this equation is given by [25]

$$\Delta f(t) = \beta \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-i(t-s)\mathcal{L}_0} (i\mathcal{L}_0 A) f_{\text{eq}} \mathcal{F}(s) ds, \quad (2.5)$$

where $\beta = 1/(k_B T)$ is the thermodynamic beta. With this expression at hand, we can construct the total distribution function $f(t)$ and compute the time-dependent expectation value $\langle B \rangle(t) = \int d\Gamma B f(t)$ of another arbitrary phase-space observable $B = B(q, p)$. After inserting the distribution function and several intermediate calculation steps, we obtain

$$\langle B \rangle(t) = \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \beta \int_{-\infty}^t \frac{d}{dt} \langle AB(t-s) \rangle_{\text{eq}} \mathcal{F}(s) ds \quad (2.6)$$

as the final expression. Mathematically, this states that the change in B at time t is obtained by convolving an equilibrium time-correlation function with the external perturbation [25]. Since it is linear in the perturbation, it is referred to as a linear response relation.

Eq. (2.6) is a manifestation of the fluctuation–dissipation theorem [15]. It relates the system’s nonequilibrium response to weak perturbations (dissipative part) to its internal equilibrium fluctuations, which are quantified by a time-correlation function evaluated within the equilibrium ensemble. A key limitation of this relation is its linear nature. It is valid only near equilibrium and cannot capture the system’s response to stronger perturbations, where nonlinear effects become significant. Describing such nonlinear responses requires the development of extended frameworks beyond linear response theory.

Before introducing a nonlinear response formalism, we first want to specify the physical system we aim to study in this work.

2.2. System Setup

The system we investigate is composed of N stochastic degrees of freedom $\mathbf{y} = (y^{(1)}, \dots, y^{(N)})$, where $y^{(i)}$ denotes the i -th component. We couple them to a heat bath at temperature T and prepare the system in equilibrium at time $s = t_0$. To drive the system away from equilibrium for times $s > t_0$, we couple it to a time-dependent d -dimensional control parameter

$$\mathbf{x}_s \equiv \begin{pmatrix} x_s^1 \\ \vdots \\ x_s^d \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad (2.7)$$

which follows the driving protocol $\chi = (\mathbf{x}_s, t_0 \leq s \leq t)$ over the time interval $[t_0, t]$. Hence, the degrees of freedom \mathbf{y}_s evolve in time under its influence.

The control parameter contains $d \in \mathbb{N}^*$ deterministic driving components and thus represents a multidimensional perturbation. The coupling between \mathbf{y}_s and \mathbf{x}_s is described by the potential energy function $U(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)$, which we allow to depend arbitrarily on both arguments. This general formulation naturally includes the possibility of a nonlinear coupling between the system and the perturbation. Because we prepared it in equilibrium, the control parameter takes the value \mathbf{x}_{t_0} for times $s \leq t_0$. In this case, the system is fully characterized by the Boltzmann distribution associated with $U(\mathbf{y}, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})$.

In general, this setup is nearly identical to that used in the one-dimensional driving case [16, 24]. To keep the framework applicable to different nonequilibrium situations, we leave the system as general as possible without specifying further details. Compared to a scalar control parameter, the presented form allows for perturbations with multiple components, such as magnetic or electric fields.

2.3. Nonlinear Response Theory within Path Integral Formalism

To describe the system's behavior far away from equilibrium, we derive general nonlinear response relations within a path integral formalism. Because the driving protocol is time-dependent, observables depend on the entire path the stochastic degrees of freedom take, rather than only on their current state (memory effects).

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The path integral framework captures this trajectory dependence by averaging over all possible paths the system can take, each weighted by its respective probability.

The formulation presented in this chapter follows the works of Boris Müller [26] and of Matthias Krüger and Juliana Caspers [14, 16, 24], with modifications that extend the formalism to multidimensional driving.

2.3.1. Nonlinear Response via Equilibrium Averages

The external driving causes the stochastic degrees of freedom to follow the path $\omega = (\mathbf{y}_s, t_0 \leq s \leq t)$ during the time interval $[t_0, t]$. The expectation value of any observable $O(\chi, \omega)$, which depends on the protocol and path¹, is given by [16]

$$\langle O \rangle = \int \mathcal{D}\omega \mathcal{P}(\chi, \omega) O(\chi, \omega). \quad (2.8)$$

$\mathcal{D}\omega$ denotes the path element, while $\mathcal{P}(\chi, \omega)$ represents the path weight, which contains the distribution function of the perturbation ensemble. We can express the path weight as [16]

$$\mathcal{P}(\chi, \omega) = e^{-\mathcal{A}(\chi, \omega)} \mathcal{P}_{eq}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \omega), \quad (2.9)$$

where $\mathcal{P}_{eq}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \omega)$ denotes the path weight of the corresponding equilibrium ensemble, and $\mathcal{A}(\chi, \omega)$ is the perturbation action. Since \mathcal{P}_{eq} corresponds to equilibrium, the protocol is fixed at \mathbf{x}_{t_0} and it contains the Boltzmann distribution, while \mathcal{A} quantifies the deviation from the equilibrium state due to the perturbation.

To make further progress, we can decompose the perturbation action into a time-antisymmetric part $S(\chi, \omega)$ and a time-symmetric part $D(\chi, \omega)$ [27],

$$\mathcal{A} = D - \frac{1}{2}S, \quad D \equiv \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{A} + \mathcal{A}\theta), \quad S \equiv \mathcal{A}\theta - \mathcal{A}. \quad (2.10)$$

These two components are defined through the time reversal operator [16]

$$(\theta\chi, \theta\omega)_s = (\pi\mathbf{x}_{t+t_0-s}, \pi\mathbf{y}_{t+t_0-s}), \quad (2.11)$$

which reverses the temporal direction of both the path and the protocol. π denotes the kinematical time reversal, which flips the sign of velocities. Applying θ to both

¹Hence, it is referred to as a path observable.

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parts of the action yields

$$S(\theta\chi, \theta\omega) = -S(\chi, \omega) \quad \text{and} \quad D(\theta\chi, \theta\omega) = D(\chi, \omega), \quad (2.12)$$

which motivates the terminology. By using that the system was prepared in equilibrium at time t_0 and the invariance of the equilibrium distribution under time reversal, $\mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \theta\omega) = \mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \omega)$, we can express the time-antisymmetric component from Eq. (2.10) as the logarithm of the ratio of path weights:

$$S = \mathcal{A}(\theta\chi, \theta\omega) - \mathcal{A}(\chi, \omega) = \ln \frac{e^{-\mathcal{A}(\chi, \omega)} \mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \omega)}{e^{-\mathcal{A}(\theta\chi, \theta\omega)} \mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \theta\omega)} = \ln \frac{\mathcal{P}(\chi, \omega)}{\mathcal{P}(\theta\chi, \theta\omega)}. \quad (2.13)$$

Expanding the action in Eq. (2.10) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A} &= \mathcal{A}' + \frac{\mathcal{A}''}{2} + \frac{\mathcal{A}'''}{6} + \dots \\ &= \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{2} \left(D'' - \frac{S''}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{6} \left(D''' - \frac{S'''}{2}\right) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

To recover the equilibrium path weight $\mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \omega)$ for a vanishing perturbation, we assume $\mathcal{A}^{(0)} = D^{(0)} - \frac{S^{(0)}}{2} = 0$. Inserting Eq. (2.14) into the perturbed path weight, Eq. (2.9), and expanding the exponential gives

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P}(\chi, \omega) &= \left[1 - \mathcal{A}' - \frac{1}{2}(\mathcal{A}'' - (\mathcal{A}')^2) - \frac{1}{6}(\mathcal{A}''' - 3\mathcal{A}'\mathcal{A}'' + (\mathcal{A}')^3) + \dots \right] \mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \omega) \\ &= \left[1 - \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(D'' - \frac{S''}{2}\right) - \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2}\right)^2 \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{6} \left[\left(D''' - \frac{S'''}{2}\right) - 3 \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2}\right) \left(D'' - \frac{S''}{2}\right) + \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2}\right)^3 \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \dots \right] \mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \omega). \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

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Using this expression, Eq. (2.8) evaluates to

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle O \rangle &= \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \left[\left\langle \left(D'' - \frac{S''}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2} \right)^2 O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{6} \left[\left\langle \left(D''' - \frac{S'''}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - 3 \left\langle \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2} \right) \left(D'' - \frac{S''}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \left\langle \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2} \right)^3 O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] + \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{2.16}$$

Eq. (2.16) is the nonlinear response of any path observable O . We observe that its expressed in terms of equilibrium averages² $\langle F(\chi, \omega) \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \int \mathcal{D}\omega \mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \omega) F(\chi, \omega)$, where the protocol is fixed at \mathbf{x}_{t_0} .

To derive an analogous relation for the time-reversed observable $O\theta$, we need to consider the temporal symmetry of the action components, Eq. (2.12), and the already mentioned reversibility of the equilibrium distribution. The latter directly implies that the equilibrium state is invariant under time reversal, i.e., $\langle F(\theta\chi, \theta\omega) \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \langle F(\chi, \omega) \rangle_{\text{eq}}$ holds. The nonlinear response relation for the time-reversed path observable then reads

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle O\theta \rangle &= \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle \left(D' + \frac{S'}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \left[\left\langle \left(D'' + \frac{S''}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle \left(D' + \frac{S'}{2} \right)^2 O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{6} \left[\left\langle \left(D''' + \frac{S'''}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - 3 \left\langle \left(D' + \frac{S'}{2} \right) \left(D'' + \frac{S''}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \left\langle \left(D' + \frac{S'}{2} \right)^3 O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] + \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{2.17}$$

Once again, the response is entirely expressed in terms of equilibrium averages.

Instead of a path observable, we can consider the special case of a state observable $O_t(\chi, \omega) = O(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{y}_t)$, which only depends on the end of the path. To obtain a corresponding nonlinear response relation, we evaluate the difference between Eq. (2.16) and Eq. (2.17) for $O = O_t$. Due to being only dependent on the end of the path, we define the expectation value of the time-reversed state observable as [16]

$$\langle (O\theta)_t \rangle \equiv \int \mathcal{D}\omega e^{-\mathcal{A}(\theta\chi, \theta\omega)} \mathcal{P}_{\text{eq}}(\mathbf{x}_{t_0}, \theta\omega) O(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{y}_t). \tag{2.18}$$

By applying the definition of the time reversal operator (2.11) and using the prop-

² $F(\chi, \omega)$ serves as an example of another arbitrary path observable.

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erties of equilibrium, we find

$$\langle (O\theta)_t \rangle = \langle O_t \rangle = \langle O_{t_0} \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \langle O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}}. \quad (2.19)$$

The nonlinear response of the state observable O_t is then given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O_t - (O\theta)_t \rangle &= \langle O_t \rangle - \langle O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &= \langle S'O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\langle S''O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - 2\langle D'S'O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] + \frac{1}{6} \left[\langle S'''O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - 3\langle (D'S'' + D''S')O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \left(3(D')^2S' + \frac{(S')^3}{4} \right) O_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2.20)$$

2.3.2. Nonlinear Response via Equilibrium Joint Cumulants

As we have seen, the nonlinear responses of both path observables and state observables, Eqs. (2.16) and (2.20), are entirely expressed in terms of equilibrium averages. In some special application cases, it has been observed that for large times t the terms in Eq. (2.20) diverge independently [14]. Analytically, this can be avoided by reformulating the response in terms of equilibrium joint cumulants $\langle \cdot; \dots; \cdot \rangle_{\text{eq}}$, which we refer to as *connected correlation functions (CCFs)* [14, 16, 24]. This approach can be applied to both state and path observables. The mathematical definition of joint cumulants, along with the derivation steps leading to the modified response relations, are provided in Appendix A.

The path response $\langle O \rangle = \langle O(\chi, \omega) \rangle$ and the state response $\langle O_t \rangle = \langle O(\mathbf{x}_t, \mathbf{y}_t) \rangle$, in terms of equilibrium joint cumulants, are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O \rangle &= \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \langle S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\langle D'; D'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{4} \langle S''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{8} \langle S'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle O_t \rangle &= \langle O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle S'; O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \langle S''; O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; S'; O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \left[\langle D'; S''; O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \langle D''; S'; O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \langle D'; D'; S'; O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{24} \langle S'; S'; S'; O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{6} \langle S'''; O_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

In the following, we will work with these modified response relations.

2.4. Volterra Series Expansion

We will see that the nonlinear response and fluctuations under strong external driving, obtained from Eqs. (2.21) and (2.22), can be cast into a functional expansion around the reference equilibrium state of the system. This expansion does not take the simple form of a Taylor series, due to the time-dependent protocol. Instead, it must account for the memory effects, and is known as a *Volterra series expansion*. In this subsection we want to briefly introduce the mathematical formulation.

Formally, the Volterra series is a functional expansion that quantifies the response of a nonlinear system with memory to an arbitrary input [28, 29]. The key difference from a Taylor series is that the system's response at a given time depends on the input at all previous times, rather than only on the input at the current time. For a causal³ and time-varying system, the expansion is given by [29]

$$\begin{aligned}
 y(t) = & h_0(t) + \int_{t_0}^t d\tau_1 h_1(t, \tau_1)x(\tau_1) + \int_{t_0}^t d\tau_1 \int_{t_0}^{\tau_1} d\tau_2 h_2(t, \tau_1, \tau_2)x(\tau_1)x(\tau_2) \\
 & + \int_{t_0}^t d\tau_1 \int_{t_0}^{\tau_1} d\tau_2 \int_{t_0}^{\tau_2} d\tau_3 h_3(t, \tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3)x(\tau_1)x(\tau_2)x(\tau_3) + \dots,
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.23}$$

where y is the output, representing the nonlinear response to the input x over the time interval $[t_0, t]$. This expansion gives rise to functions $h_0(t), h_1(t, \tau_1), h_2(t, \tau_1, \tau_2), \dots$, which are named Volterra kernels (or memory kernels) and characterize how past inputs contribute to the system's response [29]. The form of the Volterra series used here reflects that the system dynamics vary in time, making the kernels explicitly dependent not only on the integration times $\tau_1, \tau_2, \tau_3, \dots$, but also on the observation time t .

The representation in Eq. (2.23) is unique only if the Volterra kernels are symmetric in the integration variables for each fixed observation time t [29]. To enforce this property, the n -th order kernel $h_n(t, \tau_1, \dots, \tau_n)$ can always be replaced by its symmetrized form [29]

$$h_n^{\text{sym}}(t, \tau_1, \dots, \tau_n) \equiv \frac{1}{n!} \sum_{\pi \in S_n} h_n(t, \tau_{\pi(1)}, \dots, \tau_{\pi(n)}),
 \tag{2.24}$$

where the sum runs over all elements π in the symmetric group S_n , i.e., the group of all permutations of n elements. This symmetrization leaves the expansion in Eq. (2.23) unchanged.

³A system is considered causal, when its output does not depend on future inputs.

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To study the system introduced in Sec. 2.2, we introduce the observable conjugate to the driving protocol. We define it as the gradient of the potential U with respect to $\mathbf{x}_s \in \mathbb{R}^d$,

$$\mathbf{F}_s \equiv \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s) \equiv \nabla_{\mathbf{x}_s} U(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s) \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad (3.1)$$

with i -th component

$$F_s^i \equiv \frac{\partial U(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^i} \quad \text{for } i = 1, \dots, d. \quad (3.2)$$

The physical interpretation of \mathbf{F}_s depends on the specific form of U and thus on the nature of the applied perturbation. In the special case where the control parameter components x_s^i represent spatial coordinates, \mathbf{F}_s denotes (minus) the force acting on the multidimensional control parameter \mathbf{x}_s . From this point onward, we will refer to it as the *generalized force*.

When the system is driven far away from equilibrium, its statistical properties are described by the quantities $\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t_1}; \dots; \mathbf{F}_{t_m} \rangle$, which we name *generalized connected correlation functions (GCCFs)*. They depend on another arbitrary state observable $B_t = B(\mathbf{y}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$ and the generalized force $\mathbf{F}_{\tilde{t}} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{y}_{\tilde{t}}, \mathbf{x}_{\tilde{t}})$ at times $\tilde{t} = t_1, \dots, t_m$. Since the generalized force is a vector-valued observable, the GCCFs need to be mathematically distinct from the joint cumulants introduced in Sec. 2.3.2 and Appendix A.

This work aims to explicitly define these functions and show that they can be represented as nonlinear Volterra series expansions around the system's reference equilibrium state.

3.1. Microscopic Action Components

To apply the response relations Eqs. (2.21) and (2.22), we need to further clarify the two action components S and D . A basic assumption we make, is that the system satisfies the condition of *local detailed balance*. One physical formulation of this condition is that the time-antisymmetric part of the perturbation action, as given in Eq. (2.13), is equal to the entropy change of the bath relative to the reference equilibrium state [30]. Hence, S is also referred to as the *entropic component* of the action [27].

In our case, this change originates from the multidimensional protocol that drives the system out of equilibrium. Analogous to Refs. [16, 24], a simple expression for the entropy change can be obtained by analyzing the system's thermodynamics. We start from the time-dependent Hamiltonian

$$H(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0}) = \underbrace{U(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})}_{\equiv H_0(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})} + \underbrace{U(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s) - U(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})}_{\equiv H_1(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})}, \quad (3.3)$$

describing the total energy of the system at time s . We separate the Hamiltonian into two contributions, H_0 and H_1 . The term $H_0(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})$ corresponds to the equilibrium part of the energy, evaluated in the unperturbed ensemble for the fixed control parameter value \mathbf{x}_{t_0} . The second contribution $H_1(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})$ is the perturbation Hamiltonian, which quantifies the energy change of the system relative to the equilibrium state.

The total energy change over the entire driving period $[t_0, t]$ reads $\Delta H = H(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})|_{t_0}^t$. However, the condition of local detailed balance establishes only a connection between the time-antisymmetric action part and the entropy change connected to the perturbation-dependent part of the energy [30]. Therefore, we only need to evaluate the change of the perturbation Hamiltonian $\Delta H_1 = H_1(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})|_{t_0}^t$. On the other hand, ΔH_1 can be obtained from the first law of thermodynamics [1]

$$\Delta H_1 = W + Q, \quad (3.4)$$

where Q is the energy transferred from the bath to the system in form of heat and W is the work applied through the external protocol. Combining both approaches

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yields

$$\Delta H_1 = H_1(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s, \mathbf{x}_{t_0})|_{t_0}^t = W + Q. \quad (3.5)$$

For the work applied we find

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \int_{t_0}^t ds \dot{\mathbf{x}}_s \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{x}_s} U = \int_{t_0}^t ds \dot{\mathbf{x}}_s \cdot \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s) = \int_{t_0}^t ds \sum_{i=1}^d \dot{x}_s^i F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s) \\ &= \int_{t_0}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s), \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

where $\dot{\mathbf{x}}_s = \frac{d}{dt}\mathbf{x}_s \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denotes the protocol velocity. In Eq. (3.6) we introduced the *Einstein summation convention* [31] to simplify the notation of the appearing dot product¹ in the integrand. By inserting Eq. (3.6) into Eq. (3.5), the entropy change $S = -\beta Q$ (with $\beta = 1/(k_B T)$) can be written as

$$S = \beta(-\Delta H_1 + W) = \beta \left[U(\mathbf{y}_t, \mathbf{x}_{t_0}) - U(\mathbf{y}_t, \mathbf{x}_t) + \int_{t_0}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s) \right]. \quad (3.7)$$

In theory, we could now write down the desired expansion of S . However, this remains challenging because of the two potential boundary terms in Eq. (3.7). We can simplify the expansion by preparing the system in equilibrium in the infinite past, i.e., $t_0 \rightarrow -\infty$ and by choosing the final value of the control parameter equal to its initial value, $\mathbf{x}_{t_0} = \mathbf{x}_t$. With this choice we do not influence the system at time t and we can perform the expansion around the equilibrium state corresponding to \mathbf{x}_t [16, 23, 24].

Then Eq. (3.7) simplifies to

$$S = \beta \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s) \stackrel{(2.13)}{=} \ln \frac{\mathcal{P}(\chi, \omega)}{\mathcal{P}(\theta\chi, \theta\omega)}. \quad (3.8)$$

The last equality once again emphasizes the assumption of local detailed balance, which establishes the connection between the system's thermodynamics and the perturbation action from the path integral formalism.

The expansion of Eq. (3.8) is still complicated, since the components of the generalized force $F_s^i = F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)$ all explicitly depend on the multidimensional control parameter. This leads to a nonlinear dependence of S on the driving velocity components \dot{x}_s^i , which can be seen by expanding F_s^i around the equilibrium state, i.e.,

¹This is the standard dot product on \mathbb{R}^d , because both $\dot{\mathbf{x}}_s, \mathbf{F}_s \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

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in powers of $(x_s^i - x_{t_0}^i)$. Using our simplification $x_{t_0}^i = x_t^i$, this can equivalently be written as an expansion in powers of $(x_s^i - x_t^i)$. We find

$$\begin{aligned}
F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s) &= F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_t) + \frac{\partial F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^j} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t} (x_s^j - x_t^j) + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^j \partial x_s^k} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t} \\
&\quad \times (x_s^j - x_t^j)(x_s^k - x_t^k) + \dots \tag{3.9} \\
&= F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_t) - \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_{s'}^j \Theta(s' - s) \frac{\partial F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^j} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t} \\
&\quad + \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \Theta(s' - s) \Theta(s'' - s) \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^j \partial x_s^k} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t} + \dots \tag{3.10}
\end{aligned}$$

To display the nonlinearity in the driving velocity we used the identity² $x_s^j - x_t^j = -\int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_{s'}^j \Theta(s' - s)$ iteratively, which is the component-wise generalization of the relation used in the scalar protocol case [16, 24]. Inserting the expanded generalized force components from Eq. (3.10) into Eq. (3.8) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
S &= \beta \underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_t)}_{\equiv S'} - 2\beta \underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \frac{\partial F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^j} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t} \Theta(s' - s)}_{\equiv S''} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \\
&\quad + 3\beta \underbrace{\int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \frac{\partial^2 F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^j \partial x_s^k} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t} \Theta(s' - s) \Theta(s'' - s)}_{\equiv S'''} \cdot \frac{1}{6} \\
&\quad + \dots \tag{3.11}
\end{aligned}$$

$$= S' + \frac{S''}{2} + \frac{S'''}{6} + \dots \tag{3.12}$$

For clarity, we once again repeat the defined microscopic expansion coefficients:

$$S' = \beta \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_t) \tag{3.13}$$

$$S'' = -2\beta \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \frac{\partial F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^j} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t} \Theta(s' - s) \tag{3.14}$$

$$S''' = 3\beta \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \frac{\partial^2 F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)}{\partial x_s^j \partial x_s^k} \Big|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t} \Theta(s' - s) \Theta(s'' - s) \tag{3.15}$$

² $\Theta(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & t < 0 \\ 1, & t \geq 0 \end{cases}$ denotes the Heaviside function.

⋮

Since all generalized force components and their partial derivatives are evaluated at the fixed control parameter value \mathbf{x}_t , we redefine³ $F_s^i \equiv F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)|_{\mathbf{x}_s=\mathbf{x}_t}$ to simplify the notation in the future.

The time-symmetric part of the action D depends on the dynamics of the system. Hence, without a more detailed specification of the system, its exact form cannot be stated. Since it is not related to thermodynamics, its also named *non-thermodynamic* or *frenetic* component [27]. To match the form of the time-antisymmetric part, we assume a general notation $D = D' + \frac{D''}{2} + \dots$ with expansion coefficients

$$D' = \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \mathcal{D}_s^i \quad (3.16)$$

$$D'' = \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \mathcal{D}_{s,s'}^{i,j} \quad (3.17)$$

⋮

The coefficients \mathcal{D}_s^i and $\mathcal{D}_{s,s'}^{i,j}$ are unknown coefficients, which can only be determined when examining a specific system. For our purpose we do not need to specify them any further.

In general, the expansions of S and D can be continued to arbitrary higher order. Here, we restrict ourselves to the coefficients required to evaluate the response relations in Eqs. (2.21) and (2.22) up to the given order. By extending the response relations to higher order, one would also require higher-order expansion coefficients of the action parts.

3.2. Generalized Connected Correlation Functions (GCCFs)

The GCCFs are mathematically distinct from the CCFs⁴, which were the relevant quantities in the one-dimensional driving case [16, 24]. Since \mathbf{F}_s is vector-valued and B_t is scalar, these functions need to take the form of higher-dimensional objects that capture the properties of all d driving components. To establish a general definition of the GCCF $\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t_1}; \dots; \mathbf{F}_{t_m} \rangle$ of order $m + 1$, containing the generalized force m

³Note that with this definition the meaning of F_s^i has changed.

⁴Recall that joint cumulants and connected correlation functions (CCFs) are synonymous.

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times, we first specify the lowest order cases $m = 0, 1, 2, 3$ explicitly.

We begin with the first order ($m = 0$), which is simply the expectation value of B_t ,

$$\langle B_t \rangle \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (3.18)$$

Since it does not contain the generalized force, it is a scalar quantity. Therefore, the first-order GCCF coincides with the first-order CCF for a scalar protocol, which is the only special case of equivalence.

The second-order GCCF ($m = 1$) already must have a different structure because it contains the generalized force. It is defined as the vector

$$\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'} \rangle \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \langle B_t; F_{t'}^1 \rangle \\ \vdots \\ \langle B_t; F_{t'}^d \rangle \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^d \quad (3.19)$$

with components $(\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'} \rangle)^\alpha \equiv \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle$. It contains all d covariances between B_t and the components of the generalized force and can thus be interpreted as a covariance vector.

Continuing, we define the third order ($m = 2$) as the matrix

$$\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'}; \mathbf{F}_{t''} \rangle \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \langle B_t; F_{t'}^1; F_{t''}^1 \rangle & \langle B_t; F_{t'}^1; F_{t''}^2 \rangle & \dots & \langle B_t; F_{t'}^1; F_{t''}^d \rangle \\ \langle B_t; F_{t'}^2; F_{t''}^1 \rangle & \langle B_t; F_{t'}^2; F_{t''}^2 \rangle & \dots & \langle B_t; F_{t'}^2; F_{t''}^d \rangle \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \langle B_t; F_{t'}^d; F_{t''}^1 \rangle & \langle B_t; F_{t'}^d; F_{t''}^2 \rangle & \dots & \langle B_t; F_{t'}^d; F_{t''}^d \rangle \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d} \quad (3.20)$$

with components $(\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'}; \mathbf{F}_{t''} \rangle)^{\alpha\beta} \equiv \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha; F_{t''}^\beta \rangle$. This $d \times d$ matrix contains all d^2 three-point correlators (joint cumulants) between B_t and the components of the generalized force.

In line with this, the fourth order ($m = 3$) must be a three-index object

$$\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'}; \mathbf{F}_{t''}; \mathbf{F}_{t'''} \rangle \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d \times d}, \quad (3.21)$$

which contains all d^3 four-point correlators $(\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'}; \mathbf{F}_{t''}; \mathbf{F}_{t'''} \rangle)^{\alpha\beta\gamma} \equiv \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha; F_{t''}^\beta; F_{t'''}^\gamma \rangle$.

These expressions show an emerging pattern, which allows us to state the general

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structure for arbitrary order. The lowest-order GCCF, $\langle B_t \rangle \in \mathbb{R}$, is a scalar, i.e. a rank-0 object. Following up, the second order $\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'} \rangle \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is a vector, corresponding to a rank-1 object. The third order $\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'}; \mathbf{F}_{t''} \rangle \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ is a matrix, corresponding to a rank-2 object. Finally, the fourth order $\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t'}; \mathbf{F}_{t''}; \mathbf{F}_{t'''} \rangle \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d \times d}$ is a rank-3 object.

In general, we observe that the GCCF $\langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_{t_1}; \dots; \mathbf{F}_{t_m} \rangle$ of order $m + 1$ corresponds to an m -index quantity, which we refer to as a rank- m object in the sense of index notation. Formally, these objects follow the same rank hierarchy as tensors. However, we cannot directly classify the GCCFs as tensors, since we do not have any knowledge of their transformation properties under coordinate changes, which is the defining property of tensors [32]. Instead, we regard the GCCFs as *tensor-like objects*, which share the rank hierarchy of tensors but not necessarily their transformation properties. The components $\langle B_t; F_{t_1}^{\alpha_1}; \dots; F_{t_m}^{\alpha_m} \rangle$ of this rank- m tensor-like object are once again joint cumulants. This means that the GCCFs are constructed from ordinary CCFs.

To compute important quantities, such as the three-point correlator $\langle F_t^i; F_t^i; F_t^i \rangle$ of an individual generalized force component at time t , we must include the special case $B_t = F_t^i$ in our formulation. This is the reason why $B_t(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)$ is defined to depend explicitly on the control parameter.

3.3. Nonlinear Volterra Series Expansion

3.3.1. Formulation of the Expansions

We aim to construct the first four GCCFs, Eqs. (3.18)–(3.21). To this end, it is sufficient to calculate a single arbitrary component⁵ of each, as this fully determines the corresponding GCCF. As in the one-dimensional driving case, their scalar components can be expanded into nonlinear Volterra series when the system is out of equilibrium. These expansions are expressed in powers of the driving velocity components \dot{x}_s^i and performed around the equilibrium state corresponding to \mathbf{x}_t [14, 16, 24]. To perform these expansions we will apply the derived nonlinear response relations. We compute the expectation value of B_t with Eq. (2.21) and higher order components with Eq. (2.22).

⁵When referring to the components of the lowest-order GCCF, we simply mean $\langle B_t \rangle$ itself.

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The Volterra series expansions of the components read

$$\begin{aligned} \beta \langle B_t \rangle &= \Gamma^{(0,0)} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left(\Gamma_{t-s}^{(0,1)} \right)_i + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s'}^{(0,2)} \right)_{ij} \\ &+ \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s',t-s''}^{(0,3)} \right)_{ijk} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \beta^2 \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle &= \left(\Gamma_{t-t'}^{(1,0)} \right)^\alpha + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left(\Gamma_{t-s;t-t'}^{(1,1)} \right)_i^\alpha \\ &+ \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s';t-t'}^{(1,2)} \right)_{ij}^\alpha + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

$$\beta^3 \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha; F_{t''}^\beta \rangle = \left(\Gamma_{t-t',t-t''}^{(2,0)} \right)^{\alpha\beta} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left(\Gamma_{t-s;t-t',t-t''}^{(2,1)} \right)_i^{\alpha\beta} + \dots \quad (3.24)$$

$$\beta^4 \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha; F_{t''}^\beta; F_{t'''}^\gamma \rangle = \left(\Gamma_{t-t',t-t'',t-t'''}^{(3,0)} \right)^{\alpha\beta\gamma} + \dots \quad (3.25)$$

⋮

The derivation steps of the expansions are given in Appendix B. For structural reasons, each component carries a factor of $\beta = 1/(k_B T)$ to the power of its order. While the expansions can in principle be extended to arbitrary order, we restrict ourselves to the orders shown above. Further expansion would require us to extend the nonlinear response relations to higher order and to formulate the corresponding higher-order action components, which is a long-winded process. Furthermore, we assume that the components of higher order GCCFs can be expanded in the same way. It is important to remember that the expansions, Eqs. (3.22)—(3.25), are written using the Einstein summation convention, where repeated indices are implicitly summed over⁶.

These expansions give rise to memory kernels $\Gamma_{t-s_1, \dots, t-s_n; t-t_1, \dots, t-t_m}^{(m,n)}$ with components $\left(\Gamma_{t-s_1, \dots, t-s_n; t-t_1, \dots, t-t_m}^{(m,n)} \right)_{i_1, \dots, i_n}^{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m}$. Analogous to Refs. [16, 24], we label the kernels such that $m+1$ reflects the order of the GCCF, while n denotes the expansion order in the driving velocity. These kernels also have the structure of tensor-like objects. We observe that a kernel characterized by the sum $m+n$ is a $(m+n)$ -index quantity. This means it corresponds to a rank- $(m+n)$ tensor-like object with d^{m+n} components. For example, $\Gamma^{(1,1)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}$ needs to be a $d \times d$ matrix with d^2 components.

⁶Recall that the generalized force has d components F_s^1, \dots, F_s^d .

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Formally, the kernel components can be defined as

$$\left(\Gamma_{t-s_1, \dots, t-s_n; t-t_1, \dots, t-t_m}^{(m, n)}\right)_{i_1, \dots, i_n}^{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m} \equiv \frac{\beta^{m+1}}{n!} \frac{\delta^n}{\delta \dot{x}_{s_1}^{i_1} \dots \delta \dot{x}_{s_n}^{i_n}} \langle B_t; F_{t_1}^{\alpha_1}; \dots; F_{t_m}^{\alpha_m} \rangle \Big|_{\{\mathbf{x}_s\}=\mathbf{x}_t}. \quad (3.26)$$

It is important to note that this is just a technical definition written down from the Volterra series expansions, Eqs. (3.22)—(3.25), containing no further microscopic information. The right-hand side is evaluated in the equilibrium state corresponding to \mathbf{x}_t (final value of the control parameter), where the driving velocity vanishes, i.e., $\dot{\mathbf{x}}_t = 0$.

The kernel components carry two sets of time-indices and two sets of component-indices, which can naturally be grouped into ordered pairs of the form (*time, component*). From the definition, Eq. (3.26), we observe that the time-indices s_1, \dots, s_n together with the component-indices i_1, \dots, i_n are associated with the functional derivatives with respect to the protocol velocity. This means, each ordered pair (s_τ, i_τ) , for $\tau = 1, \dots, n$, corresponds to one of the n insertions $\dot{x}_{s_\tau}^{i_\tau}$.

On the other hand, the time indices t_1, \dots, t_m and the component indices $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m$ are associated with the generalized force components, which can be freely chosen on the left-hand side of the expansions. Hence, each ordered pair (t_ν, α_ν) , for $\nu = 1, \dots, m$, corresponds to one of the m insertions $F_{t_\nu}^{\alpha_\nu}$.

Grouping the indices in such a way clarifies their different origins. This will become important when discussing the symmetry properties of the kernel components. To further emphasize their different roles, we adopted in the expansions a notation in which the Latin component indices i_1, \dots, i_n are written as subscripts, while the Greek component indices $\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m$ are written as superscripts. As already discussed, the Latin indices originate from functional derivatives with respect to the protocol velocity components and are therefore the ones summed over in the Volterra series. Drawing an analogy to special relativity, we write them as subscripts to indicate their contraction with the velocity components, which as defined before carry superscript indices.

In contrast, the Greek indices label the components of the generalized force which enter the components of GCCFs. Therefore they appear on both sides of the expansion, which means that they remain free indices, not summed over. To distinguish them from the summation indices, we write them as superscripts. In general, a kernel indexed by (m, n) has components which carry m free indices and n summation

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indices. However, it should be emphasized that this choice is merely a notational convention introduced to clarify the structure of the kernels. In cases where we need to sum over originally free indices, the notation can be adjusted dynamically, as will be seen later on.

To summarize, we expanded the components of the GCCFs in nonlinear Volterra series, Eqs. (3.22)–(3.25), around the reference equilibrium state with fixed control parameter value \mathbf{x}_t . These expansions take the form of power series in the driving velocity components \dot{x}_s^i and fully determine the corresponding GCCFs.

3.3.2. Microscopic Expressions for the Kernel Components

The memory kernel components can be expressed in terms of the microscopic action components S and D , derived in Sec. 3.1. They follow from the derivation of the Volterra series expansions, Eqs. (3.22)–(3.25), as presented in Appendix B.

The kernel components indexed by $m = 0$ appear in the expansion of the mean, Eq. (3.22), and are given by

$$\Gamma^{(0,0)} = \beta \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \quad (3.27)$$

$$\left(\Gamma_s^{(0,1)} \right)_i = \beta^2 \langle F_s^i; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \quad (3.28)$$

$$\left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)} \right)_{ij} = \frac{\beta^2}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left[\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \right], \quad (3.29)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(0,3)} \right)_{ijk} = & \frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left[\frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \right. \\ & + \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}} \partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(3)}) \\ & \left. - \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1), s_{\pi(2)}}}^{i_{\pi(1)}, i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) + \frac{\beta^4}{24} \langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ & \left. + \beta^2 \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(3)}) \right], \quad (3.30) \end{aligned}$$

⋮

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These components make up the higher-order memory kernels

$$\Gamma_s^{(0,1)} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \left(\Gamma_s^{(0,1)}\right)_1 \\ \vdots \\ \left(\Gamma_s^{(0,1)}\right)_d \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^d, \quad \Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)}\right)_{11} & \cdots & \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)}\right)_{1d} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)}\right)_{d1} & \cdots & \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)}\right)_{dd} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times d}, \quad \dots, \quad (3.31)$$

which are needed to calculate the full nonlinear response $\beta \langle B_t \rangle$. At this point one has to be cautious with the formulation of the generalized force components. In Sec. 3.1 we defined $F_s^i \equiv F^i(\mathbf{y}_s, \mathbf{x}_s)|_{\mathbf{x}_s = \mathbf{x}_t}$, which is used in the memory kernel components. On the other hand, the components of the GCCFs consist of terms like $F_{t'}^\alpha = F^\alpha(\mathbf{y}_{t'}, \mathbf{x}_{t'})$, which still use the standard notation due to having a different time index than s . The structure of $\Gamma^{(0,0)}$ differs from that of the higher-order kernels, as it lacks any time dependence. This is a consequence of the time-independence of equilibrium averages. In the expressions for the kernel components $\left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)}\right)_{ij}$ and $\left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(0,3)}\right)_{ijk}$ the sums run over all permutations π in the symmetric groups S_2 and S_3 , respectively. These permutations act on the previously introduced ordered pairs (s_τ, i_τ) for $\tau = 1, 2$ and $\tau = 1, 2, 3$, respectively. This procedure can be regarded as a symmetrization of the kernel components. Its origin is presented in Appendix B, and the underlying mathematical justification is discussed at the end of this section.

The kernel components indexed by $m = 1$ enter the expansion of the component-wise covariance. Eq. (3.23). They are given by

$$\left(\Gamma_{t_1}^{(1,0)}\right)^\alpha = \beta^2 \langle F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \quad (3.32)$$

$$\left(\Gamma_{s; t_1}^{(1,1)}\right)_i^\alpha = \beta^2 \left\langle \left(\mathcal{D}_s^i + \frac{\beta F_s^i}{2}\right); F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \beta^2 \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^i}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(t_1 - s), \quad (3.33)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2; t_1}^{(1,2)}\right)_{ij}^\alpha &= \frac{\beta^2}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left[\frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}, i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\ &\quad + \frac{\beta}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{\beta^2}{8} \langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad \left. + \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) \Theta(t_1 - s_{\pi(2)}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^{i_{\pi(1)}} \partial x_{t_1}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(t_1 - s_{\pi(1)}) \Theta(t_1 - s_{\pi(2)}) \right] \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \Bigg], \\
& \vdots
\end{aligned} \tag{3.34}$$

As in the expansion of the mean, these components define the higher-order memory kernels, which are needed to construct the second-order GCCF $\beta^2 \langle B_t; \mathbf{F}_t \rangle$ from its components $\beta^2 \langle B_t; F_t^\alpha \rangle$.

The kernel components indexed by $m = 2$ enter the expansion of the components of the third-order GCCF, Eq. (3.24), and are given by

$$\left(\Gamma_{t_1, t_2}^{(2,0)} \right)^{\alpha\beta} = \beta^3 \langle F_{t_1}^\alpha; F_{t_2}^\beta; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \tag{3.35}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(\Gamma_{s; t_1, t_2}^{(2,1)} \right)_i^{\alpha\beta} &= \beta^3 \left\langle \left(\mathcal{D}_s^i + \frac{\beta F_s^i}{2} \right); F_{t_1}^\alpha; F_{t_2}^\beta; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \beta^3 \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^i}; F_{t_2}^\beta; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(t_1 - s) \\
&+ \beta^3 \left\langle F_{t_1}^\alpha; \frac{\partial F_{t_2}^\beta}{\partial x_{t_2}^i}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(t_2 - s),
\end{aligned} \tag{3.36}$$

⋮

Lastly, only the zeroth-order kernel components (which are equilibrium fourth cumulants), indexed by $m = 3$ and $n = 0$, contribute to the expansion of the components of the fourth-order GCCF in Eq. (3.25). They are given by

$$\left(\Gamma_{t_1, t_2, t_3}^{(3,0)} \right)^{\alpha\beta\gamma} = \beta^4 \langle F_{t_1}^\alpha; F_{t_2}^\beta; F_{t_3}^\gamma; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \tag{3.37}$$

⋮

Overall, we observe that all kernel components are expressed as equilibrium joint cumulants of the observables of interest and the general expansion coefficients $D_s^i, D_{s, s'}^{i, j}$ of the time-symmetric part of the action. From the expansions in Eqs. (3.22)–(3.25) and the general definition in Eq. (3.26), it follows that they depend only on the time differences $t - s_1, \dots, t - s_n, t - t_1, \dots, t - t_m$, which is a direct consequence of the stationarity of equilibrium time-correlation functions [4]. Another property that follows directly from the definition of the kernel components, is that they are invariant under any permutation $\pi \in S_n$ of the n ordered pairs (s_τ, i_τ) for $\tau = 1, \dots, n$ and separately invariant under any permutation $\sigma \in S_m$ of the m ordered pairs (t_ν, α_ν) for $\nu = 1, \dots, m$. S_n and S_m denote the symmetric groups of n and m elements, respectively. Hence, the components are symmetric in

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the ordered pairs (s_τ, i_τ) and symmetric in the ordered pairs (t_ν, α_ν) . The symmetry properties for all m, n and any $\pi \in S_n, \sigma \in S_m$ can be summarized as

$$\left(\Gamma_{t-s_1, \dots, t-s_n; t-t_1, \dots, t-t_m}^{(m,n)}\right)_{i_1, \dots, i_n}^{\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m} = \left(\Gamma_{t-s_{\pi(1)}, \dots, t-s_{\pi(n)}; t-t_{\sigma(1)}, \dots, t-t_{\sigma(m)}}^{(m,n)}\right)_{i_{\pi(1)}, \dots, i_{\pi(n)}}^{\alpha_{\sigma(1)}, \dots, \alpha_{\sigma(m)}}. \quad (3.38)$$

In the microscopic expressions for the kernel components, we explicitly enforced symmetry with respect to permutations of the ordered pairs (s_τ, i_τ) by introducing the sums described above.

Lastly, we want to briefly explain why the expansions in Eqs. (3.22)–(3.25) are in fact Volterra series. The system's nonlinear mean response is given by Eq. (3.22). If the sum in the expansion is written out explicitly, the expression matches the form of the Volterra series presented in Eq. (2.23). The only differences are that we have a multidimensional input and that the kernels turn out to depend only on time differences between the observation time t and the integration times. This follows from the properties of equilibrium and therefore has a physical origin. Consequently, the symmetry properties found for the corresponding kernel components are consistent with the mathematical prediction from Eq. (2.24), modified for time differences and multidimensional inputs. The higher-order expansions in Eqs. (3.23)–(3.25), which describe the nonlinear and non-Gaussian fluctuations of the system, are also Volterra series. This can be seen by extending Eq. (2.23) to the case of multidimensional inputs and outputs.

3.4. Fluctuation-Dissipation Relations

The memory kernel components in Eqs. (3.27)–(3.30) and (3.32)–(3.37) are found to be related by a set of identities. They read

$$\left(\Gamma_t^{(0,1)}\right)_\alpha = \left(\Gamma_t^{(1,0)}\right)^\alpha \quad \text{for } \alpha = 1, \dots, d \quad (3.39)$$

$$\left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)}\right)_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left(\Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}; s_{\pi(2)}}^{(1,1)}\right)_{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(2,0)}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \quad \text{for } \alpha, \beta = 1, \dots, d \quad (3.40)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(0,3)}\right)_{\alpha\beta\gamma} &= \frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left(\Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}; s_{\pi(3)}}^{(1,2)}\right)_{\alpha_{\pi(1)} \alpha_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}} - \frac{1}{12} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left(\Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}; s_{\pi(2)}, s_{\pi(3)}}^{(2,1)}\right)_{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)} \alpha_{\pi(3)}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{6} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(3,0)}\right)^{\alpha\beta\gamma} \quad \text{for } \alpha, \beta, \gamma = 1, \dots, d. \end{aligned} \quad (3.41)$$

⋮

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These identities connect the memory kernel components appearing in the expansion of the mean, Eq. (3.22), with kernel components from the higher order expansions in Eqs. (3.23)–(3.25). They generalize the identities presented in Refs. [16, 24] to the case of multidimensional driving and are valid only if the system obeys local detailed balance. Their validity can be explicitly verified by inserting the microscopic kernel expressions, which is done in Appendix C. In formulating the identities, we have symmetrized them with respect to interchanges of the complete ordered pairs (s_τ, i_τ) and (t_ν, α_ν) . This symmetrization is required for the relations to hold mathematically.

The lowest-order identity in Eq. (3.39) relates the α -th component of the linear response of the mean $(\Gamma^{(0,1)})_\alpha$ to the equilibrium covariance (zeroth-order response) $(\Gamma^{(1,0)})^\alpha$ of B and the generalized force component F^α . For a fixed α , this statement matches the one from the fluctuation–dissipation theorem in Eq. (2.6), i.e., the linear nonequilibrium response of the mean is governed by the fluctuations in equilibrium. Thus, the identity can be understood as a component-wise fluctuation–dissipation theorem, valid independently for each $\alpha = 1, \dots, d$ and is therefore linear.

The second identity in Eq. (3.40) relates the $\alpha\beta$ -th component of the second-order response of the mean $(\Gamma^{(0,2)})_{\alpha\beta}$ to the $\alpha\beta$ -th component of the linear response of the covariance components $(\Gamma^{(1,1)})_\alpha^\beta$ and the $\alpha\beta$ -th component of the zeroth-order response of the third order GCCF components $(\Gamma^{(2,0)})^{\alpha\beta}$. The relation is nonlinear, due to connecting non-Gaussian fluctuations with nonlinear response.

The third identity in Eq. (3.41) relates the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -th component of the third-order response of the mean $(\Gamma^{(0,3)})_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ to the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -th component of the second-order response of the covariance components $(\Gamma^{(1,2)})_{\alpha\beta}^\gamma$, the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -th component of the first-order response of the third order GCCF components $(\Gamma^{(2,1)})_\alpha^{\beta\gamma}$ and the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ -th component of the zeroth-order response of the fourth order GCCF components $(\Gamma^{(3,0)})^{\alpha\beta\gamma}$. Hence, this relation is also nonlinear.

In summary, the identities in Eqs. (3.39)–(3.41) establish relations between the components of the tensor-like memory kernels that arise from the nonlinear Volterra series expansions. Once again, we emphasize that they were derived under the assumption of local detailed balance. We observe that each identity connects kernel components with the same total sum $m+n$. For instance, the component-wise FDT, Eq. (3.39) connects components of vector kernels with $m+n=1$, corresponding to a linear response relation. The second-order identity in Eq. (3.40) connects components of matrix kernels with $m+n=2$, and the third-order identity in Eq. (3.41)

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connects components of rank-three kernels with $m + n = 3$. While the first identity is a linear relation corresponding to a component-wise fluctuation–dissipation theorem, the higher-order identities, Eqs. (3.40)–(3.41), represent *component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations* that extend the component-wise FDT to regimes of stronger multidimensional driving. Both of the latter are symmetrized in the way described above. We expect that the list of identities continues to higher order, although these have not yet been calculated. To derive these, an extension of the Volterra series expansions to higher orders would be required. As already noted, these identities can be interpreted as a generalization of those presented in Refs. [16, 24], which apply to the case of a scalar driving protocol. Later on we will show, that these identities are included in the ones derived here.

We expect the component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations to hold on both microscopic and macroscopic length scales, since neither the observable B nor the generalized force components F^α have been specified. The form of the latter depends on the potential energy U . Consequently, the components F^α may represent either microscopic or macroscopic observables, depending on the applied perturbation or on how the system couples to it. Similarly, B is arbitrary and can be chosen at either scale.

3.5. Violation of the Fluctuation-Dissipation Theorem

From the Volterra series expansion of the mean, Eq. (3.22), and of the covariance components, Eq. (3.23), we can derive a response relation that quantifies the violation of the fluctuation–dissipation theorem when the system is driven away from equilibrium by the multidimensional protocol.

We begin by inserting the component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations, Eqs. (3.39)–(3.41), into $\beta\langle B_t \rangle$ and the time-integrated covariance $\beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \langle B_t; F_s^i \rangle$. The time-integrated form of Eq. (3.23) is obtained by summing

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over the index that remains free in the original expression. This yields⁷

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta\langle B_t \rangle &= \beta\langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left(\Gamma_{t-s}^{(1,0)} \right)_i + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left[\left(\Gamma_{t-s;t-s'}^{(1,1)} \right)_{ij} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{1}{2} \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s'}^{(2,0)} \right)_{ij} \right] + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \left[\left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s';t-s''}^{(1,2)} \right)_{ijk} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{6} \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s',t-s''}^{(3,0)} \right)_{ijk} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\Gamma_{t-s;t-s',t-s''}^{(2,1)} \right)_{ijk} \right] + O((\dot{x}^i)^4),
\end{aligned} \tag{3.42}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \langle B_t; F_s^i \rangle &= \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left(\Gamma_{t-s}^{(0,1)} \right)_i \\
&\quad + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left[\left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s'}^{(0,2)} \right)_{ij} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s'}^{(2,0)} \right)_{ij} \right] \\
&\quad + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \left[\left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s',t-s''}^{(0,3)} \right)_{ijk} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{1}{6} \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s',t-s''}^{(3,0)} \right)_{ijk} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\Gamma_{t-s;t-s',t-s''}^{(2,1)} \right)_{ijk} \right] + O((\dot{x}^i)^4).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.43}$$

By subtracting Eq. (3.43) from Eq. (3.42), and once again applying the component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations (3.39)–(3.41), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta\langle B_t \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \langle B_t; F_s^i \rangle &= \Gamma^{(0,0)} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s'}^{(2,0)} \right)_{ij} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \\
&\quad \times \left[\frac{1}{3} \left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s',t-s''}^{(3,0)} \right)_{ijk} - \left(\Gamma_{t-s;t-s',t-s''}^{(2,1)} \right)_{ijk} \right] \\
&\quad + O((\dot{x}^i)^4).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.44}$$

Resorting to the Volterra series expansions, Eqs. (3.22)–(3.25), the right-hand side of Eq. (3.44) can be expressed entirely in terms of the components of the GCCFs,

⁷The index notation in the kernel components is adjusted accordingly due to summing over them.

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which are joint cumulants. This yields

$$\begin{aligned}
& \underbrace{\Gamma^{(0,0)}}_{=\beta\langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}}} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left[\underbrace{\left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s'}^{(2,0)} \right)_{ij} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_{s''}^k \left(\Gamma_{t-s;t-s',t-s''}^{(2,1)} \right)_{ijk}}_{=\beta^3 \langle B_t; F_s^i; F_{s'}^j \rangle} \right] \\
& + \frac{1}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \underbrace{\left(\Gamma_{t-s,t-s',t-s''}^{(3,0)} \right)_{ijk}}_{=\beta^4 \langle B_t; F_s^i; F_{s'}^j; F_{s''}^k \rangle} + O((\dot{x}^i)^4) \\
& = \beta \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \langle B_t; F_s^i; F_{s'}^j \rangle \\
& + \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \langle B_t; F_s^i; F_{s'}^j; F_{s''}^k \rangle + O((\dot{x}^i)^4)
\end{aligned} \tag{3.45}$$

Hence, the final relation, with both sides expressed entirely in terms of joint cumulants, reads:

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta \langle B_t \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \langle B_t; F_s^i \rangle & = \beta \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \langle B_t; F_s^i; F_{s'}^j \rangle \\
& + \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \langle B_t; F_s^i; F_{s'}^j; F_{s''}^k \rangle \\
& + O((\dot{x}^i)^4).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.46}$$

This response relation expresses the difference between the mean $\beta \langle B_t \rangle$ and the time-integrated covariance $\beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \langle B_t; F_s^i \rangle$ in terms of time-integrated higher-order joint cumulants of B and the generalized force components. The summations incorporate the contributions from all d driving components. The left-hand side resembles the FDT for a multidimensional perturbation and therefore vanishes identically⁸ up to linear order in the driving velocity. The right-hand side consists of terms of higher order in the driving velocity components. Starting at second order, it shows that nonlinear and non-Gaussian fluctuations generate corrections to the linear multidimensional FDT. Hence, Eq. (3.46) can be understood as a fluctuation-identity, which quantifies the deviation from the FDT in such nonequilibrium situations.

It is important to mention, that the right-hand side of Eq. (3.46) vanishes to arbitrary order in the driving velocity if all observables B, F^1, \dots, F^d are Gaussian, since then all joint cumulants of order three or higher are zero [16, 33]. In this scenario, the FDT remains valid even under strong driving.

⁸ $\beta \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}}$ is part of the FDT.

4. Applications of the Formalism

In this chapter, we apply parts of the derived formalism to two specific cases. First, we show that the one-dimensional driving case [16, 24], which formed the foundation of this thesis, is encompassed by the generalization to multidimensional driving. Second, we consider a two-component velocity protocol and evaluate the corresponding response relation that quantifies the FDT violation.

4.1. One-Dimensional Driving

The special case of a scalar protocol corresponds to $d = 1$ in our description. Hence, both the protocol vector and the generalized force vector contain only one component, which is why they can be treated as scalars. In particular, we have $x_s \in \mathbb{R}$ and $F_s \equiv F(\mathbf{y}_s, x_s) \equiv \partial_{x_s} U(\mathbf{y}_s, x_s) \in \mathbb{R}$. As a result, the GCCFs $\langle B_t; F_{t_1}; \dots; F_{t_m} \rangle$ are scalars as well, since F is no longer a vector. Consequently, they are mathematically equivalent to joint cumulants. This means that for $d = 1$ the GCCFs reduce to the original CCFs and are no longer composed of components. Therefore, they can be directly expanded within the Volterra series framework. Accordingly, the memory kernels arising from these expansions need to be scalars as well.

When we evaluate the Volterra series expansions, Eqs. (3.22)–(3.25) for $d = 1$ and the properties discussed above, we find¹

$$\begin{aligned} \beta \langle B_t \rangle &= \Gamma^{(0,0)} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s \Gamma_{t-s}^{(0,1)} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s \dot{x}_{s'} \Gamma_{t-s, t-s'}^{(0,2)} \\ &\quad + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s \dot{x}_{s'} \dot{x}_{s''} \Gamma_{t-s, t-s', t-s''}^{(0,3)} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\beta^2 \langle B_t; F_{t'} \rangle = \Gamma_{t-t'}^{(1,0)} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s \Gamma_{t-s; t-t'}^{(1,1)} \quad (4.2)$$

$$+ \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s \dot{x}_{s'} \Gamma_{t-s, t-s'; t-t'}^{(1,2)} + \dots \quad (4.3)$$

¹The driving velocity $\dot{x}_s \in \mathbb{R}$ is now also a scalar quantity.

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$$\beta^3 \langle B_t; F_{t'}; F_{t''} \rangle = \Gamma_{t-t', t-t''}^{(2,0)} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \Gamma_{t-s; t-t', t-t''}^{(2,1)} + \dots \quad (4.4)$$

$$\beta^4 \langle B_t; F_{t'}; F_{t''}; F_{t'''} \rangle = \Gamma_{t-t', t-t'', t-t'''}^{(3,0)} + \dots \quad (4.5)$$

⋮

In accordance with the fact that all quantities have only one component, the expansions involve no summations. The explicit microscopic expressions for the appearing memory kernels can be obtained by evaluating Eqs. (3.27)–(3.30) and (3.32)–(3.37) for $d = 1$. It is important to note that in this case the symmetrization acts only on the time indices, since there are no component indices.

Consequently, the component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations in Eqs. (3.39)–(3.41) also simplify. Since the memory kernels are scalars, the identities no longer connect components and involve only the kernels themselves. Furthermore, the symmetrization reduces to interchanges of the time arguments rather than the ordered pairs. They simplify to

$$\Gamma_t^{(0,1)} = \Gamma_t^{(1,0)} \quad (4.6)$$

$$\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}; s_{\pi(2)}}^{(1,1)} - \frac{1}{2} \Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(2,0)} \quad (4.7)$$

$$\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(0,3)} = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}; s_{\pi(2)}; s_{\pi(3)}}^{(1,2)} - \frac{1}{12} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}; s_{\pi(2)}, s_{\pi(3)}}^{(2,1)} + \frac{1}{6} \Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(3,0)}. \quad (4.8)$$

⋮

Finally, we evaluate the FDT violation as given by Eq. (3.46). We obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \beta \langle B_t \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s \langle B_t; F_s \rangle &= \beta \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s \dot{x}_{s'} \langle B_t; F_s; F_{s'} \rangle \\ &+ \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s \dot{x}_{s'} \dot{x}_{s''} \langle B_t; F_s; F_{s'}; F_{s''} \rangle \\ &+ O(\dot{x}^4), \end{aligned} \quad (4.9)$$

as no summations remain in this case.

These results for $d = 1$, obtained from the multidimensional driving formalism, are in exact agreement with those shown in Refs. [16, 24]. Therefore, we conclude that the generalized formalism includes the already studied case of scalar driving.

4.2. Two-Component Velocity Protocol

Next, we examine the special case of a two-component velocity protocol ($d = 2$), in which the system is driven simultaneously along the x - and y -axis with constant velocities. Then the protocol velocity takes the form

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}_s = \begin{pmatrix} \dot{x}_s^x \\ \dot{x}_s^y \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} v_x \\ v_y \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{with} \quad v_x, v_y = \text{const.} \quad (4.10)$$

Moreover, we consider a scenario in which the driving along the x -direction is significantly stronger than along the perpendicular y -direction, such that² $v_y \ll v_x$.

The FDT violation for this specific protocol can be investigated by evaluating Eq. (3.46). The left-hand side is given by

$$\beta \langle B_t \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \langle B_t; F_s^i \rangle = \beta \langle B_t \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds \left[v_x \langle B_t; F_s^x \rangle + v_y \langle B_t; F_s^y \rangle \right], \quad (4.11)$$

where F_s^x and F_s^y denote the generalized force components corresponding to the x - and y -directions, respectively. Since the protocol velocity components are constant and thus time independent, they could in principle be moved outside the integrals when splitting the sum. However, for readability, we keep them inside the integrands. The terms of second and third order in the driving velocity, which make up the right-hand side of Eq. (3.46), are given by

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \langle B_t; F_s^i; F_{s'}^j \rangle \\ &= -\frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \left[v_x^2 \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x \rangle + v_x v_y \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x \rangle \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + v_y^2 \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^y \rangle \right] \\ & \approx -\frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \left[v_x^2 \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x \rangle + v_x v_y \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x \rangle \right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (4.12)$$

²We assume $v_x, v_y \neq 0$.

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \langle B_t; F_s^i; F_{s'}^j; F_{s''}^k \rangle \\
&= \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \left[v_x^3 \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^x \rangle + v_x^2 v_y \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^y \rangle \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y; F_{s''}^x \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^x \rangle \right) + v_x v_y^2 \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y; F_{s''}^y \rangle \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^y \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^y; F_{s''}^x \rangle \right) + v_y^3 \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^y; F_{s''}^y \rangle \right] \\
&\approx \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \left[v_x^3 \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^x \rangle + v_x^2 v_y \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^y \rangle \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y; F_{s''}^x \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^x \rangle \right) \right]. \tag{4.13}
\end{aligned}$$

In both correction contributions we invoked the driving condition $v_y \ll v_x$, neglecting terms quadratic in v_y and of higher order. By making use of Eqs. (4.11)–(4.13) we can fully evaluate Eq. (3.46). We obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \beta \langle B_t \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds v_x \langle B_t; F_s^x \rangle + \frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' v_x^2 \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x \rangle \\
&\quad - \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' v_x^3 \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^x \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds v_y \langle B_t; F_s^y \rangle \\
&= \beta \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' v_x v_y \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x \rangle \right) \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' v_x^2 v_y \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^y \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y; F_{s''}^x \rangle \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^x \rangle \right) + O(v_x^4, v_y^2), \tag{4.14}
\end{aligned}$$

which is the response relation quantifying the FDT violation for a system driven by this two-component constant velocity protocol.

If the time-integrated covariance of B and F^x does not vanish, $\int_{-\infty}^t ds v_x \langle B_t; F_s^x \rangle \neq 0$, Eq. (4.14) can be rewritten in a more compact form. To this end, we introduce the new parameter

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta_{\text{eff}}^2(v_x) \equiv & \beta^2 \left[1 + \frac{-\frac{\beta}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' v_x^2 \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x \rangle}{\int_{-\infty}^t ds v_x \langle B_t; F_s^x \rangle} \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{\frac{\beta^2}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' v_x^3 \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^x \rangle}{\int_{-\infty}^t ds v_x \langle B_t; F_s^x \rangle} \right]. \tag{4.15}
\end{aligned}$$

We refer to β_{eff} as the *effective inverse temperature*. This parameter is a technically motivated definition, serving as a tool to quantify the system's deviation from equilibrium and providing a measure of the strength of nonlinear and non-Gaussian

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fluctuations. It should not be regarded as a proper thermodynamic inverse temperature $\beta = 1/(k_B T)$, but merely as an indicator of how far the system is perturbed away from equilibrium [34, 35]. Since the system is primarily driven along the x -direction, we define β_{eff} to contain all x -only nonlinearities and therefore to depend exclusively on v_x . Thus, β_{eff} characterizes the deviation from equilibrium originating from the dominant driving component. We will see that this allows us to interpret the response relation in a new way. From Eq. (4.15) we observe that $\beta_{\text{eff}} = \beta$ is recovered for weak driving. In this case the system remains close to equilibrium, i.e. within the regime of linear response theory. This is consistent with our interpretation that β_{eff} is a measure for the deviation from equilibrium.

As already mentioned, the definition requires a non-vanishing linear response in the x -direction, $\int_{-\infty}^t ds v_x \langle B_t; F_s^x \rangle \neq 0$. If this condition is not satisfied and the leading contribution arises only at higher orders in the driving, this definition is no longer valid. In this case we must revert to the original response relation, Eq. (4.14).

By making use of the newly defined β_{eff} , Eq. (4.14) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \beta \langle B_t \rangle - \beta_{\text{eff}}^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds v_x \langle B_t; F_s^x \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds v_y \langle B_t; F_s^y \rangle \\
 &= \beta \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' v_x v_y \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x \rangle \right) \\
 &+ \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' v_x^2 v_y \left(\langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^y \rangle + \langle B_t; F_s^x; F_{s'}^y; F_{s''}^x \rangle \right. \\
 &\left. + \langle B_t; F_s^y; F_{s'}^x; F_{s''}^x \rangle \right) + O(v_y^2).
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.16}$$

The structure of this response relation is interesting. By construction, we absorbed all nonlinear correction terms involving only the x -drive into the effective inverse temperature β_{eff} . This restores an FDT-like structure for the x -response, where the linear response is now governed by β_{eff} .

Since the driving velocity in the y -direction is much smaller, all terms of order v_y^2 and higher can be neglected. Thus, the relevant y -response remains linear and is still controlled by the inverse bath temperature β .

Therefore, the left-hand side of Eq. (4.16) can be interpreted as an effective FDT, where β_{eff} governs the pure x -drive and β the pure y -drive. From this point of view, the violation of this effective FDT is solely caused by the nonequilibrium coupling between the x - and y -drives and is quantified by the right-hand side of Eq. (4.16) (beyond the equilibrium contribution $\beta \langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}}$). These two leading-order corrections

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involve higher-order joint cumulants containing both generalized force components F^x and F^y , and cannot be neglected since they are linear³ in v_y .

Finally, as a consistency check, we confirm that Eq. (4.16) reduces to the known one-dimensional result in the limit $v_y \rightarrow 0$. For $v_x \equiv v$, $v_y = 0$, $F_s^x \equiv F_s$, and $F_s^y = 0$ we find

$$\beta \langle B_t \rangle - \beta_{eff}^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds v \langle B_t; F_s \rangle = \beta \langle B \rangle_{eq}. \quad (4.17)$$

As expected, all contributions from the pure y -drive and mixed drive vanish. Re-inserting the definition of β_{eff} , Eq. (4.15), yields

$$\begin{aligned} \beta \langle B_t \rangle - \beta^2 \int_{-\infty}^t ds v \langle B_t; F_s \rangle &= \beta \langle B \rangle_{eq} - \frac{\beta^3}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' v^2 \langle B_t; F_s; F_{s'} \rangle \\ &+ \frac{\beta^4}{6} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' v^3 \langle B_t; F_s; F_{s'}; F_{s''} \rangle \\ &+ O(v^4). \end{aligned} \quad (4.18)$$

We exactly recover the result found in the scalar driving case [16, 36] for a constant-velocity protocol $\dot{x}_s \equiv v$.

In summary, we rewrote the response relation quantifying the violation of the FDT into a modified response relation which quantifies the violation of an effective FDT, where the x -response is governed by β_{eff} and the y -response by β . The nonequilibrium deviation arises from the coupling between the two drives, where the leading-order corrections are linear in v_y and involve time-integrated higher-order joint cumulants.

³To be precise, the first correction term is linear in v_y and v_x and the second correction term is linear in v_y and quadratic in v_x .

5. Summary and Outlook

The aim of this thesis was to investigate the nonequilibrium evolution of a system strongly driven away from equilibrium by a multidimensional, time-dependent protocol. In particular, the goal was to generalize the formalism introduced by Juliana Caspers and Matthias Krüger in Refs. [16, 24], which was originally developed for a scalar protocol, to the case of a multidimensional protocol with d driving components.

First, we introduced the setup of the system under investigation and defined the deterministic multidimensional control parameter that represented the external perturbation. We included the possibility that the perturbation couples nonlinearly to the system and did not specify the physical parameters in detail to keep the framework as general as possible.

To describe the system's nonlinear response and nonlinear fluctuations, we introduced the path integral formalism. Within this framework, response relations were derived for both path and state observables, first expressed in terms of equilibrium averages and later reformulated through equilibrium joint cumulants of the time-symmetric and time-antisymmetric parts of the perturbation action. To apply these relations to the system, explicit microscopic expressions for the action parts were obtained. We assumed that the system obeyed local detailed balance, which connected the time-antisymmetric action component to the entropy change of the bath. Meanwhile the time-symmetric component was represented in a matching general form.

Following this, the generalized connected correlation functions (GCCFs) were introduced. We stated that they are the relevant quantities that capture the statistical properties of the system out of equilibrium and can be interpreted as a generalization of the connected correlation functions (CCFs) from the scalar protocol case. By explicitly defining the first few orders, we showed that they take the form of multi-indexed, tensor-like objects. This analysis revealed that their components are, once again, ordinary CCFs and hence joint cumulants.

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Furthermore, we investigated the nonequilibrium forms of the components of the first few GCCFs. We showed that they can be expanded in nonlinear Volterra series around the system's reference equilibrium state, which fully determine the corresponding GCCFs. These expansions gave rise to memory kernels, which themselves took the form of tensor-like objects with distinct components. We provided a general macroscopic definition of these components and discussed their symmetry properties. Afterwards, explicit microscopic expressions for them were derived in terms of the two action components

We showed that the memory kernel components are connected through a set of identities. The lowest-order identity corresponded to a linear relation and was interpreted as a component-wise fluctuation–dissipation theorem (FDT), while the higher-order identities took the form of component-wise nonlinear relations. Hence, we referred to them as component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations. We also speculated on their applicability at both macroscopic and microscopic length scales.

In addition, a response relation, quantifying the deviation from the FDT under multidimensional driving, was derived from the Volterra series expansions of the GCCF components.

In the final part of the thesis, we applied the formalism to two specific examples. First, it was shown that in the special case $d = 1$, the framework reduces to the original results for one-dimensional driving. Afterwards, we evaluated the FDT violation for a constant-velocity protocol with $d = 2$ components, where the system was driven more strongly along one direction than along the perpendicular one. For a non-vanishing linear response along the strongly driven direction, we interpreted the nonlinear and non-Gaussian fluctuations of the system far from equilibrium in terms of an effective inverse temperature. This theoretical construct provided a measure of the system's deviation from the equilibrium state. In this way, we cast the response into an FDT-like form, which led to a new interpretation of the response relation as the violation of an effective FDT. We observed that this deviation arose solely from the nonequilibrium coupling of the two drives.

There are many interesting directions that future work could take. First, it would be important to investigate whether the GCCFs and the memory kernels can be classified as real tensors, either in a general setting or for specific systems. This would require a detailed study of their transformation properties.

On the experimental side, the component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation

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relations need to be tested, which includes verifying their applicability on both microscopic and macroscopic length scales.

Another point of interest is the further generalization of the formalism when B is promoted to a vector-valued observable. This would result in a new, more complex mathematical structure of the system. The present work should provide the foundation for this generalization.

Moreover, the study of the system driven by the constant-velocity protocol can be extended. The final response relation involves third- and fourth-order joint cumulants, which are analytically challenging to handle. Without further assumptions about the system, we cannot state their properties. It would be interesting to explore possible simplifications of this relation, either through analytical approaches or by studying the system under additional symmetry assumptions. Numerical simulations also offer a promising way for further investigations, which could lay the foundation for future experimental validation of the FDT violation.

A. Joint Cumulants and Modified Response Relations

A.1. Definition of Joint Cumulants

The joint cumulant or connected correlation function of N random variables X_1, \dots, X_N , denoted by $\kappa(X_1, \dots, X_N) \equiv \langle X_1; \dots; X_N \rangle$, is defined as [33]

$$\langle X_1; \dots; X_N \rangle \equiv \sum_{\pi} (|\pi| - 1)! (-1)^{|\pi|-1} \prod_{B \in \pi} \left\langle \prod_{i \in B} X_i \right\rangle. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

In this definition π ranges over all partitions of the set $\{1, \dots, N\}$, B denotes a block of the partition π and $|\pi|$ is the number of blocks in the partition π . By evaluating this expression for a specific N , we find the joint cumulant of N random variables, expressed as a sum of products of mixed moments [33]. The first few orders¹, $N = 1, 2, 3, 4$, read as follows:

$$\langle X \rangle = \langle X \rangle, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\langle X; Y \rangle = \langle XY \rangle - \langle X \rangle \langle Y \rangle = \text{Cov}(X, Y), \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle X; Y; Z \rangle &= \langle XYZ \rangle - \langle XY \rangle \langle Z \rangle - \langle XZ \rangle \langle Y \rangle - \langle YZ \rangle \langle X \rangle \\ &\quad + 2 \langle X \rangle \langle Y \rangle \langle Z \rangle, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle X; Y; Z; W \rangle &= \langle XYZW \rangle - \langle X \rangle \langle YZW \rangle - \langle Y \rangle \langle XZW \rangle - \langle Z \rangle \langle XYW \rangle \\ &\quad - \langle W \rangle \langle XYZ \rangle - \langle XY \rangle \langle ZW \rangle - \langle XZ \rangle \langle YW \rangle - \langle XW \rangle \langle YZ \rangle \\ &\quad + 2 \left(\langle XY \rangle \langle Z \rangle \langle W \rangle + \langle XZ \rangle \langle Y \rangle \langle W \rangle + \langle XW \rangle \langle Y \rangle \langle Z \rangle \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \langle YZ \rangle \langle X \rangle \langle W \rangle + \langle YW \rangle \langle X \rangle \langle Z \rangle + \langle ZW \rangle \langle X \rangle \langle Y \rangle \right) \\ &\quad - 6 \langle X \rangle \langle Y \rangle \langle Z \rangle \langle W \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

¹We will be using a maximum order of $N = 4$.

As expected, the joint cumulant of a single random variable is just its mean, while the joint cumulant of two random variables corresponds to their covariance. Higher-order joint cumulants represent more complex correlation measures.

A.2. Derivation of the Nonlinear Response via Equilibrium Joint Cumulants

In the following, we briefly sketch how the modified response relation, Eq. (2.21), for the path observable is derived. We begin by decomposing the path response into its time-symmetric and time-antisymmetric components:

$$\langle O \rangle = \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}\langle O + O\theta \rangle}_{\text{symmetric}} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2}\langle O - O\theta \rangle}_{\text{antisymmetric}}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

By combining Eqs. (2.16) and (2.17), we obtain the two new response relations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}\langle O + O\theta \rangle &= \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2}\left\langle \left(D'' - (D')^2 - \frac{(S')^2}{4} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{6}\left\langle \left[D''' - 3D'D'' - \frac{3}{4}S'S'' + (D')^3 + \frac{3}{4}D'(S')^2 \right] O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2}\langle O - O\theta \rangle &= \frac{1}{2}\langle S'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2}\left\langle \left(\frac{S''}{2} - D'S' \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{4}\left\langle \left[\frac{S'''}{3} - D'S'' - D''S' + (D')^2S' + \frac{(S')^3}{12} \right] O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

As before, these relations must hold for any path observable, and thus also for $O = 1$. This observable is trivially time-symmetric, and its average is independent of the system's state, as it is always equal to 1. Therefore its nonequilibrium average is equal to its equilibrium one, $\langle 1 \rangle = \langle 1 \rangle_{\text{eq}}$.

Applying $O = 1$ to Eqs. (A.7) and (A.8), while using the discussed properties, yields a set of identities:

$$\langle D' \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \langle S' \rangle_{\text{eq}} = 0, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$\left\langle D'' - (D')^2 - \frac{(S')^2}{4} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} = 0, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\left\langle \frac{S''}{2} - D'S' \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} = 0, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

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$$\left\langle D''' - 3D'D'' - \frac{3}{4}S'S'' + (D')^3 + \frac{3}{4}D'(S')^2 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} = 0, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\left\langle \frac{S'''}{3} - D'S'' - D''S' + (D')^2S' + \frac{(S')^3}{12} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} = 0. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

By using this list of identities, we can re-express the individual terms in Eq. (2.16) in terms of the joint cumulants from Eqs. (A.2)—(A.5). The first term can be expressed directly as

$$\begin{aligned} -\left\langle \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} &= \frac{1}{2} \langle S'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \langle S'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\langle S' \rangle_{\text{eq}} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} - \langle D'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \underbrace{\langle D' \rangle_{\text{eq}} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \langle S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.14})$$

For the second term we find

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{2} \left[\left\langle \left(D'' - \frac{S''}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2} \right)^2 O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] &= \frac{1}{4} \langle S''O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \langle (D')^2 O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D'S'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{8} \langle (S')^2 O \rangle_{\text{eq}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.15})$$

The terms on the right-hand side can be expressed in terms of joint cumulants. We find

$$\langle S''O \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \langle S''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle S'' \rangle_{\text{eq}} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\langle D''O \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \langle D''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle D'' \rangle_{\text{eq}} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \quad (\text{A.17})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle (D')^2 O \rangle_{\text{eq}} &= \langle D'; D'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle (D')^2 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle D'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \underbrace{\langle D' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \\ &\quad + \langle D'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \underbrace{\langle D' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} - 2 \underbrace{\langle D' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \underbrace{\langle D' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \langle D'S'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} &= \langle D'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle D'S' \rangle_{\text{eq}} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle D'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \underbrace{\langle S' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \\ &\quad + \langle S'O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \underbrace{\langle D' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} - 2 \underbrace{\langle D' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \underbrace{\langle S' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.19})$$

A. Joint Cumulants and Modified Response Relations

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle (S')^2 O \rangle_{\text{eq}} &= \langle S'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle (S')^2 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle S' O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \underbrace{\langle S' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \\
&\quad + \langle S' O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \underbrace{\langle S' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} - 2 \underbrace{\langle S' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \underbrace{\langle S' \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.20}$$

Next, we sum up all of these terms and multiply them by the corresponding prefactors from Eq. (A.15). We obtain (already omitting all vanishing terms)

$$\begin{aligned}
&\frac{1}{4} \langle S'' O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D'' O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \langle (D')^2 O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D' S' O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{8} \langle (S')^2 O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&= \frac{1}{4} \langle S''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \langle D'; D'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{8} \langle S'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\left\langle D'' - (D')^2 - \frac{(S')^2}{4} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \underbrace{\left\langle \frac{S''}{2} - D' S' \right\rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=0} \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.21}$$

The final expression for the second term reads

$$\begin{aligned}
-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left\langle \left(D'' - \frac{S''}{2} \right) O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle \left(D' - \frac{S'}{2} \right)^2 O \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] &= \frac{1}{4} \langle S''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \langle D'; D'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{8} \langle S'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{A.22}$$

The third order term in Eq. (2.16) (and higher-order terms, which are already left out in the expansion) can be treated in the same way. Here, we restrict ourselves to the results presented, as the third-order term is already cumbersome to derive. Plugging Eqs. (A.14) and (A.22) into the path response, Eq. (2.16), yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle O \rangle &= \langle O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \langle S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\langle D'; D'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{4} \langle S''; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{8} \langle S'; S'; O \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots,
\end{aligned} \tag{A.23}$$

which is exactly Eq. (2.21).

The nonlinear response of a state observable in terms of equilibrium joint cumulants, Eq. (2.22), can be derived in an analogous way from Eq. (2.20). The details are omitted here, as the derivation is essentially the same.

B. Derivation of the Volterra Series Expansions

This appendix presents the derivations of the Volterra series expansions of the mean and covariance components. The expansions of the third- and fourth-order GCCF components follow the same procedure as the covariance expansion and are therefore omitted for brevity.

B.1. Expansion of the Mean

The expansion of the mean $\beta\langle B_t \rangle$ can be formulated by evaluating Eq. (2.22) for the state observable $B_t = B(\mathbf{y}_t, \mathbf{x}_t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle B_t \rangle &= \langle B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \langle S''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} [\langle D'; S''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad + \langle D''; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}}] + \frac{1}{2} \langle D'; D'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{24} \langle S'; S'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{6} \langle S'''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

In the next step, we rewrite the individual terms by inserting the action components, Eqs. (3.13)–(3.17), and grouping them according to the driving order. From the resulting expressions, we can then identify the memory kernel components.

The zeroth-order kernel is obtained directly as

$$\beta\langle B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \beta\langle B \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \Gamma^{(0,0)}, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where we used that equilibrium averages are time-independent.

B. Derivation of the Volterra Series Expansions

The first order in the driving velocity is also given by a single term and reads

$$\begin{aligned}
\beta \langle S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} &= \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \beta^2 \langle F_s^i; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \beta^2 \langle F_{s-t}^i; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \beta^2 \langle F_{t-s}^i; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left(\Gamma_{t-s}^{(0,1)} \right)_i,
\end{aligned} \tag{B.3}$$

where the first-order memory kernel components can be identified as

$$\left(\Gamma_s^{(0,1)} \right)_i = \beta^2 \langle F_s^i; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}. \tag{B.4}$$

In the calculation steps, we first used the determinacy of the protocol to take \dot{x}_s^i outside the covariance. Afterwards, we employed the stationarity of equilibrium time-correlation functions [4] to introduce a time shift by $-t$ and finally applied the time-reversal symmetry of the equilibrium state, which was already used in Sec. 2.3.1. This requires taking into account how the observables in the joint cumulants transform under time reversal. The transformation properties follow from the action components, Eqs. (3.13)–(3.17), because S', S'', S''' need to be time-antisymmetric and D', D'' need to be time-symmetric. These operations will also be applied in all of the following calculations.

The second-order contribution to the Volterra series expansion comes from the terms $\frac{1}{2} \langle S''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}}$. For the first term, we find

$$\frac{1}{2} \langle S''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} = - \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \beta \left\langle \frac{\partial F_s^i}{\partial x_s^j}; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s' - s). \tag{B.5}$$

On the other hand, we could also write

$$\frac{1}{2} \langle S''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} = - \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \beta \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s'}^j}{\partial x_s^i}; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - s'), \tag{B.6}$$

where we exchanged the ordered index pairs $(s, i) \leftrightarrow (s', j)$. Hence, it follows that

$$\beta \left\langle \frac{\partial F_s^i}{\partial x_s^j}; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s' - s) = \beta \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s'}^j}{\partial x_s^i}; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - s'), \tag{B.7}$$

B. Derivation of the Volterra Series Expansions

which shows that the kernel components must be symmetric in the ordered index pairs of (*time, component*). They are not symmetric under exchange of only the time indices or only the component indices, since swapping just one of them alters the velocity prefactors and thereby mismatches the kernel components, even though the total expression remains unchanged. By incorporating this symmetry property, we find

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{\beta}{2} \langle S''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \beta \langle D'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&= -\frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \beta^2 \left\langle \frac{\partial F_s^i}{\partial x_s^j}; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s' - s) \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \beta^2 \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s'}^j}{\partial x_{s'}^i}; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - s') \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \beta^2 \langle \mathcal{D}_s^i; F_{s'}^j; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \beta^2 \langle \mathcal{D}_{s'}^j; F_s^i; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \frac{\beta^2}{2} \left[\langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s}^i; F_{t-s'}^j; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{t-s}^i}{\partial x_{t-s}^j}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s' - s) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s'}^j; F_{t-s}^i; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{t-s'}^j}{\partial x_{t-s'}^i}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - s') \right] \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \frac{\beta^2}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left[\langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{j_{\pi(2)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{j_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \right] \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left(\Gamma_{t-s, t-s'}^{(0,2)} \right)_{ij}, \tag{B.8}
\end{aligned}$$

with the second-order memory kernel components

$$\left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)} \right)_{ij} = \frac{\beta^2}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left[\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{j_{\pi(2)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{j_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \right]. \tag{B.9}$$

The third-order contribution to the expansion arises from the remaining terms in Eq. (B.1). As for the second order, we symmetrize the expression with respect to the interchange of the ordered pairs. We obtain¹

$$-\frac{\beta}{2} \left[\langle D'; S''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \langle D''; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right] + \frac{\beta}{2} \langle D'; D'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{\beta}{24} \langle S'; S'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}}$$

¹Since the full expression is rather lengthy, we present the derivation here only in a compact form.

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$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{\beta}{6} \langle S''' ; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
& = \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \frac{1}{6} \left[\beta^2 \left\langle \mathcal{D}_s^i ; \frac{\partial F_{s'}^j}{\partial x_{s'}^k} ; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s'' - s') + \dots \right. \\
& + \beta^2 \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s''}^k ; \frac{\partial F_{s'}^j}{\partial x_{s'}^i} ; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - s') - \frac{\beta^2}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s,s'}^{i,j} ; F_{s''}^k ; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \dots \\
& - \frac{\beta^2}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s'',s'}^{k,j} ; F_s^i ; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{\beta^2}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_s^i ; \mathcal{D}_{s'}^j ; F_{s''}^k ; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots + \frac{\beta^2}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s''}^k ; \mathcal{D}_{s'}^j ; F_s^i ; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
& + \frac{\beta^4}{24} \langle F_s^i ; F_{s'}^j ; F_{s''}^k ; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots + \frac{\beta^4}{24} \langle F_{s''}^k ; F_{s'}^j ; F_s^i ; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
& + \frac{\beta^2}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_s^i}{\partial x_s^j \partial x_s^k} ; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s' - s) \Theta(s'' - s) + \dots \\
& + \frac{\beta^2}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{s''}^k}{\partial x_{s''}^j \partial x_{s''}^i} ; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s' - s'') \Theta(s - s'') \left. \right] \\
& = \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left[\frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}} ; \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}} ; F_{t-s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}} ; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \right. \\
& + \left. \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}} \partial x_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}} ; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \right. \\
& - \left. \langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(1)}, t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}, i_{\pi(2)}} ; F_{t-s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}} ; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) + \frac{\beta^4}{24} \langle F_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}} ; F_{t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}} ; F_{t-s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}} ; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
& + \beta^2 \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}} ; \frac{\partial F_{t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}} ; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \left. \right] \\
& = \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \left(\Gamma_{t-s, t-s', t-s''}^{(0,3)} \right)_{ijk}, \tag{B.10}
\end{aligned}$$

with the third-order memory kernel components

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(0,3)} \right)_{ijk} & = \frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left[\frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}} ; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}} ; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}} ; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \right. \\
& + \left. \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}} \partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}} ; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(3)}) \right. \\
& - \left. \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}, i_{\pi(2)}} ; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}} ; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) + \frac{\beta^4}{24} \langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}} ; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}} ; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}} ; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}
\end{aligned}$$

B. Derivation of the Volterra Series Expansions

$$+ \beta^2 \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{i_{\pi(3)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(3)}) \Big]. \quad (\text{B.11})$$

By combining the results from Eqs. (B.2), (B.3), (B.8) and (B.10), we obtain the Volterra series expansion of the mean:

$$\begin{aligned} \beta \langle B_t \rangle &= \Gamma^{(0,0)} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left(\Gamma_{t-s}^{(0,1)} \right)_i + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left(\Gamma_{t-s, t-s'}^{(0,2)} \right)_{ij} \\ &+ \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \int_{-\infty}^t ds'' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \dot{x}_{s''}^k \left(\Gamma_{t-s, t-s', t-s''}^{(0,3)} \right)_{ijk} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.12})$$

The expansion and the corresponding memory kernel components are exactly those presented in Sections 3.3.1 and 3.3.2.

B.2. Expansion of the Covariance Components

To derive the expansion of the covariance components $\beta^2 \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle = \beta^2 \langle B(\mathbf{y}_t, \mathbf{x}_t); F^\alpha(\mathbf{y}_{t'}, \mathbf{x}_{t'}) \rangle$, we first need to expand $F^\alpha(\mathbf{y}_{t'}, \mathbf{x}_{t'})$ around the reference equilibrium state, i.e., around $\mathbf{x}_{t'} = \mathbf{x}_t$. The expansion is obtained by slightly modifying Eq. (3.10):

$$\begin{aligned} F^\alpha(\mathbf{y}_{t'}, \mathbf{x}_{t'}) &= F_{t'}^\alpha - \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \frac{\partial F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i} \Theta(s - t') \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \frac{\partial^2 F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i \partial x_{t'}^j} \Theta(s - t') \Theta(s' - t') + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

At this point, we need to clarify the notation, which may seem a bit confusing but is necessary for presenting the kernel components in a compact form later on. On the left-hand side, we use the standard definition $F_{t'}^\alpha = F^\alpha(\mathbf{y}_{t'}, \mathbf{x}_{t'})$. On the right-hand side, however, we introduce the modified definition $F_{t'}^\alpha \equiv F^\alpha(\mathbf{y}_{t'}, \mathbf{x}_{t'})|_{\mathbf{x}_{t'} = \mathbf{x}_t}$, as already done in Sec. 3.1. While this double use of the symbol $F_{t'}^\alpha$ may at first seem problematic, only the standard definition on the left-hand side enters explicitly into the Volterra series expansions, whereas the modified definition on the right-hand side appears solely in the microscopic expressions for the memory kernels. In summary, the symbols must be read carefully, with attention to which side of the equation they appear on in the derivation. This notation was introduced in Refs. [14, 16, 24], and developing a clearer alternative may be a subtle but interesting point for future work.

B. Derivation of the Volterra Series Expansions

Inserting Eq. (B.13) into the covariance components yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle B(\mathbf{y}_t, \mathbf{x}_t); F^\alpha(\mathbf{y}_{t'}, \mathbf{x}_{t'}) \rangle &= \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle - \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i} \right\rangle \Theta(s - t') \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial^2 F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i \partial x_{t'}^j} \right\rangle \Theta(s - t') \Theta(s' - t') \\
&\quad + \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{B.14}$$

To proceed, we evaluate the three covariance terms that appear. The first takes the form

$$\langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle = \langle B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle - \langle B_t \rangle \langle F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle. \tag{B.15}$$

The nonequilibrium averages can be further simplified by applying the nonlinear response relation for a path observable, Eq. (2.21). This yields

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle &= \langle B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle D' - \frac{S'}{2}; B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} [\langle D'; D'; B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; S'; B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}}] \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''; B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{4} \langle S''; B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{8} \langle S'; S'; B_t F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots,
\end{aligned} \tag{B.16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle B_t \rangle \langle F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle &= \left[\langle B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle D' - \frac{S'}{2}; B_t \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} [\langle D'; D'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}}] \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{4} \langle S''; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{8} \langle S'; S'; B_t \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots \right] \cdot \left[\langle F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \left\langle D' - \frac{S'}{2}; F_{t'}^\alpha \right\rangle + \frac{1}{2} [\langle D'; D'; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \langle D'; S'; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}}] - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{4} \langle S''; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{8} \langle S'; S'; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \dots \right].
\end{aligned} \tag{B.17}$$

For the expansion of the covariance components, we restrict ourselves to terms up to second order in the driving velocity. In this case, inserting Eqs. (B.16) and (B.17) into Eq. (B.15) and re-expressing the result in terms of joint cumulants, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle &= \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle D' - \frac{S'}{2}; B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D''; B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{4} \langle S''; B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \langle D'; D'; B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{8} \langle S'; S'; B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle D'; S'; B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle_{\text{eq}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{B.18}$$

The same method can be applied to the other two covariance terms in Eq. (B.14),

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which then simplify to

$$\left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i} \right\rangle = \left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} - \left\langle D' - \frac{S'}{2}; B_t; \frac{\partial F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}}, \quad (\text{B.19})$$

$$\left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial^2 F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i \partial x_{t'}^j} \right\rangle = \left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial^2 F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i \partial x_{t'}^j} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}}. \quad (\text{B.20})$$

Consequently, the second and third term in Eq. (B.14) read

$$\begin{aligned} & - \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i} \right\rangle \Theta(s - t') \\ &= - \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - t') \\ & \quad + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \left\langle D' - \frac{S'}{2}; B_t; \frac{\partial F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - t'), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.21})$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial^2 F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i \partial x_{t'}^j} \right\rangle \Theta(s - t') \Theta(s' - t') \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \left\langle B_t; \frac{\partial^2 F_{t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t'}^i \partial x_{t'}^j} \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - t') \Theta(s' - t'). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.22})$$

Combining Eqs. (B.18), (B.21) and (B.22), we obtain the final expansion. The calculation follows analogous steps as in the expansion of the mean:

$$\begin{aligned} \beta^2 \langle B_t; F_{t'}^\alpha \rangle &= \beta^2 \langle F_{t-t'}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i \beta^2 \left[\left\langle \left(\mathcal{D}_{t-s}^i + \frac{\beta F_{t-s}^i}{2} \right); F_{t-t'}^\alpha; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{t-t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t-t'}^i}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s - t') \right] \\ & \quad + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j \frac{\beta^2}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left[\frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t-t'}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\ & \quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(1)}, t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}, i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t-t'}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{\beta}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t-t'}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{\beta^2}{8} \langle F_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{t-s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t-t'}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle F_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{t-t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t-t'}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{t-t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t-t'}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - t') \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{t-t'}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t-t'}^{i_{\pi(1)}} \partial x_{t-t'}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - t') \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - t') \\
& + \frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{t-s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; F_{t-t'}^\alpha; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \Big] \\
& = (\Gamma_{t-t'}^{(1,0)})^\alpha + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \dot{x}_s^i (\Gamma_{t-s;t-t'}^{(1,1)})_i^\alpha \\
& + \int_{-\infty}^t ds \int_{-\infty}^t ds' \dot{x}_s^i \dot{x}_{s'}^j (\Gamma_{t-s,t-s';t-t'}^{(1,2)})_{ij}^\alpha + \dots, \tag{B.23}
\end{aligned}$$

where we identify the memory kernel components

$$(\Gamma_{t_1}^{(1,0)})^\alpha = \beta^2 \langle F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}, \tag{B.24}$$

$$(\Gamma_{s;t_1}^{(1,1)})_i^\alpha = \beta^2 \left\langle \left(\mathcal{D}_s^i + \frac{\beta F_s^i}{2} \right); F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \beta^2 \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^i}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(t_1 - s), \tag{B.25}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2; t_1}^{(1,2)})_{ij}^\alpha & = \frac{\beta^2}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left[\frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}, i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\
& + \frac{\beta}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{\beta^2}{8} \langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
& + \left. \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) \Theta(t_1 - s_{\pi(2)}) \right. \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{t_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{t_1}^{i_{\pi(1)}} \partial x_{t_1}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(t_1 - s_{\pi(1)}) \Theta(t_1 - s_{\pi(2)}) \\
& \left. + \frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{i_{\pi(2)}}}; F_{t_1}^\alpha; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \right]. \tag{B.26}
\end{aligned}$$

The expansions of the third- and fourth-order GCCF components can be derived in the same way as the covariance expansion, except that they involve multiple generalized force components, which must first be expanded around equilibrium. The rest of the calculation then proceeds analogously.

C. Validity of the Fluctuation-Dissipation Relations

The component-wise nonlinear fluctuation–dissipation relations, Eqs. (3.39)–(3.41), can be verified by inserting the microscopic expressions for the kernel components, Eqs. (3.27)–(3.30) and (3.32)–(3.37), into them.

The component-wise FDT in Eq. (3.39) can be seen to hold without calculation, simply by inspecting the kernel components in Eqs. (3.28) and (3.32):

$$\left(\Gamma_t^{(0,1)}\right)_\alpha = \beta^2 \langle F_t^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} = \left(\Gamma_t^{(1,0)}\right)^\alpha. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

The validity of the second identity in Eq. (3.40) follows from the calculation

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left(\Gamma_{s_{\pi(1); s_{\pi(2)}}}^{(1,1)}\right)_{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}} - \frac{1}{2} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(2,0)}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \\ &= \frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\sum_{\pi \in S_2} \left[\left\langle \left(\mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}} + \frac{\beta F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}{2} \right); F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \right] - \beta \langle F_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) \\ &= \frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\left\langle \left(\mathcal{D}_{s_1}^\alpha + \frac{\beta F_{s_1}^\alpha}{2} \right); F_{s_2}^\beta; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_2}^\beta}{\partial x_{s_2}^\alpha}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_2 - s_1) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left\langle \left(\mathcal{D}_{s_2}^\beta + \frac{\beta F_{s_2}^\beta}{2} \right); F_{s_1}^\alpha; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{s_1}^\beta}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_1 - s_2) - \beta \langle F_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) \\ &= \frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{s_1}^\beta}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_1 - s_2) + \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_2}^\beta; F_{s_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_2}^\beta}{\partial x_{s_2}^\alpha}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_2 - s_1) + \underbrace{\frac{\beta}{2} \langle F_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{\beta}{2} \langle F_{s_2}^\beta; F_{s_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}}_{=\beta \langle F_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

C. Validity of the Fluctuation-Dissipation Relations

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \beta \langle F_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \Big) \\
&= \frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_1}^\alpha}{\partial x_{s_1}^\beta}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_1 - s_2) + \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_2}^\beta; F_{s_1}^\alpha; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_2}^\beta}{\partial x_{s_2}^\alpha}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_2 - s_1) \right) \\
&= \frac{\beta^2}{2} \sum_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}_2} \left(\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \right) \\
&= \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2}^{(0,2)} \right)_{\alpha\beta}. \tag{C.2}
\end{aligned}$$

Checking the validity of the third identity in Eq. (3.41) is a bit more cumbersome. As a first step, we explicitly write down the individual terms:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}_3} \left(\Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}; s_{\pi(3)}}^{(1,2)} \right)_{\alpha_{\pi(1)} \alpha_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}} \\
&= \frac{\beta^2}{12} \sum_{\pi \in \mathcal{S}_3} \left[\frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\
&\quad - \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}, \alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} - \frac{1}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}, s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}, \alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{\beta}{2} \langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta^2}{8} \langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} + \frac{\beta^2}{8} \langle F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \\
&\quad + \left(\frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}} \partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}} \partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \\
&\quad + \frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)})
\end{aligned}$$

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$$+ \frac{\beta}{2} \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \Bigg], \quad (\text{C.3})$$

$$\frac{1}{6} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(3,0)} \right)^{\alpha\beta\gamma} = \frac{\beta^4}{6} \left\langle F_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; F_{s_3}^\gamma; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}}, \quad (\text{C.4})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{12} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left(\Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}; s_{\pi(2)}; s_{\pi(3)}}^{(2,1)} \right)_{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)} \alpha_{\pi(3)}} &= \frac{\beta^3}{12} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left[\left\langle \left(\mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}} + \frac{\beta F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}{2} \right); F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\ &+ \left\langle \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \\ &\left. + \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(3)} - s_{\pi(1)}) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

Adding these three terms gives

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left(\Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}; s_{\pi(2)}; s_{\pi(3)}}^{(1,2)} \right)_{\alpha_{\pi(1)} \alpha_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}} + \frac{1}{6} \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(3,0)} \right)^{\alpha\beta\gamma} - \frac{1}{12} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left(\Gamma_{s_{\pi(1)}; s_{\pi(2)}; s_{\pi(3)}}^{(2,1)} \right)_{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)} \alpha_{\pi(3)}} \\ &= \frac{\beta^2}{12} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left(\left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}} \partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right. \\ &\quad \times \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(3)}) - \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}, \alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\beta^2}{4} \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + 2 \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(3)}) \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{\beta^4}{6} \left\langle F_{s_1}^\alpha; F_{s_2}^\beta; F_{s_3}^\gamma; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &= \frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left[\frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}} \partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(3)}) - \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}, \alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) - \frac{\beta^4}{8} \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{\beta^4}{6} \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \beta^2 \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(3)}) \right] \end{aligned}$$

C. Validity of the Fluctuation-Dissipation Relations

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{6} \sum_{\pi \in S_3} \left[\frac{\beta^2}{2} \left(\left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} + \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}} x_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(2)}) \right. \\
&\quad \times \Theta(s_{\pi(1)} - s_{\pi(3)}) - \left. \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}, s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}, \alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \right) + \frac{\beta^4}{24} \left\langle F_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}; F_{s_{\pi(3)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \\
&\quad + \beta^2 \left\langle \mathcal{D}_{s_{\pi(1)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(1)}}; \frac{\partial F_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(2)}}}{\partial x_{s_{\pi(2)}}^{\alpha_{\pi(3)}}}; B_0 \right\rangle_{\text{eq}} \Theta(s_{\pi(2)} - s_{\pi(3)}) \left. \right] \\
&= \left(\Gamma_{s_1, s_2, s_3}^{(0,3)} \right)_{\alpha\beta\gamma}, \tag{C.6}
\end{aligned}$$

which confirms the identity.

For clarity, we have omitted some of the initial calculation steps, as they follow the same logic as in the case of the second identity.

Bibliography

- [1] H. D. Young and R. A. Freedman. *University Physics with Modern Physics*. Pearson, 2019.
- [2] R. Brown. A brief account of microscopical observations made in the months of june, july and august 1827, on the particles contained in the pollen of plants; and on the general existence of active molecules in organic and inorganic bodies. *Philos. Mag.*, 4(21):161–173, 1828.
- [3] Shuichi Kinoshita. Introduction to nonequilibrium phenomena. In *Pattern Formations and Oscillatory Phenomena*, pages 1–59. Elsevier, 2013.
- [4] R. Zwanzig. *Nonequilibrium Statistical Mechanics*. Oxford University Press, 2001.
- [5] L. E. Reichl. *A Modern Course in Statistical Physics*. Wiley-VCH, 2016.
- [6] M. Ghassemi and A. Shahidian. *Nano and Bio Heat Transfer and Fluid Flow*. Academic Press, 2017.
- [7] R. Kubo, M. Toda, and N. Hashitsume. *Statistical Physics II: Nonequilibrium Statistical Mechanics*. Springer, 1991.
- [8] A. T. McDonald R. W. Fox and P. J. Pritchard. *Introduction to Fluid Mechanics*. John Wiley & Sons, 2003.
- [9] J. K. G. Dhont. *An Introduction to Dynamics of Colloids*, volume 2. Elsevier, 1996.
- [10] D. Michieletto and M. Marendia. Rheology and viscoelasticity of proteins and nucleic acids condensates. *JACS Au*, 2(7):1506–1521, 2022.
- [11] H. Ebata, K. Nishizawa, F. A. S. van Esterik, Y. Tao, S. Inokuchi, H. Ise, and D. Mizuno. Single power-law rheology of crowded cytoplasm in living cells. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2504.18922, 2025.

Bibliography

- [12] J. C. P. Hollister, A. C. Wang, W. Kim, C.C Giza, M. L. Prins, and H. P. Kavehpour. Shear thinning behavior of cerebrospinal fluid with elevated protein or cellular concentration. *Front. Phys.*, 11:1308136, 2015.
- [13] P. Oswald. *Rheophysics: The Deformation and Flow of Matter*. Cambridge University Press, 2009.
- [14] J. Caspers and M. Krüger. Nonlinear langevin functionals for a driven probe. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 161(12):124109, 2024.
- [15] R. Kubo. The fluctuation-dissipation theorem. *Rep. Prog. Phys.*, 29(1):255, 1966.
- [16] J. Caspers and M. Krüger. Identities for nonlinear memory kernels. *Phys. Rev. E*, 112(2):024124, 2025.
- [17] A. Ghadai and P. K. Bera S. Majumdar. Instability and stress fluctuations of a probe driven through a wormlike micellar fluid. *J. Rheol.*, 69(5):599–609, 2025.
- [18] H. Seyforth, M. Gomez, W. B. Rogers, J. L. Ross, and W. W. Ahmed. Nonequilibrium fluctuations and nonlinear response of an active bath. *Phys. Rev. Res.*, 4(2):023043, 2022.
- [19] R. Kubo. Statistical-mechanical theory of irreversible processes. i. general theory and simple applications to magnetic and conduction problems. *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 12(6):570–586, 1957.
- [20] J. C. Dyre. Maximum-entropy ansatz for nonlinear-response theory. *Phys. Rev. A*, 40(4):2207–2210, 1989.
- [21] M. te Vrugt and R. Wittkowski. Mori-zwanzig projection operator formalism for far-from-equilibrium systems with time-dependent hamiltonians. *Phys. Rev. E*, 99(6):062118, 2019.
- [22] U. Basu, M. Krüger, A. Lazarescu, and C. Maes. Frenetic aspects of second order response. *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 17(9):6653–6666, 2015.
- [23] M. Krüger and C. Maes. The modified langevin description for probes in a nonlinear medium. *J. Phys. Condens. Matter*, 29(6), 2016.

Bibliography

- [24] J. Caspers. *Stochastic dynamics of driven Brownian particles in viscoelastic solvents*. Phd thesis, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Göttingen, 2024.
- [25] J.-P. Hansen and I. R. McDonald. *Theory of simple liquids: with applications to soft matter*. Academic Press, 2013.
- [26] B. Müller. *Brownian Particles in Nonequilibrium Solvents*. Phd thesis, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Göttingen, 2019.
- [27] C. Maes. Response theory: a trajectory-based approach. *Front. Phys*, 8:229, 2020.
- [28] M. Schetzen. *The Volterra and Wiener Theories of Nonlinear Systems*. John Wiley & Sons Inc, 1980.
- [29] W. J. Rugh. *Nonlinear System Theory: The Volterra-Wiener Approach*. Johns Hopkins University Press, 1981.
- [30] C. Maes. Local detailed balance. *SciPost Phys. Lect. Notes*, 32, 2021.
- [31] A. Einstein. Die grundlage der allgemeinen relativitätstheorie. *Annalen der Physik*, 49(7):769–822, 1916.
- [32] D. E. Neuenschwander. *Tensor Calculus for Physics: A Concise Guide*. Johns Hopkins University Press, 2014.
- [33] G. Peccati and M. S. Taqqu. *Wiener Chaos: Moments, Cumulants and Diagrams*. Springer, 2011.
- [34] V. Démery and É. Fodor. Driven probe under harmonic confinement in a colloidal bath. *J. Stat. Mech.*, 2019:033202, 2019.
- [35] L. F. Cugliandolo. The effective temperature. *J. Phys. A: Math. Theor*, 44(48):483001, 2011.
- [36] J. Caspers, K. K. Kumar, C. Bechinger, and M. Krüger. Panoscopic non-equilibrium fluctuation identity. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:2502.10175, 2025.

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Declaration on the use of ChatGPT and comparable tools

In this thesis, I have used ChatGPT or comparable AI tools exclusively for proofreading, optimizing self-written text passages, and brainstorming. I hereby declare that I have stated all uses completely.

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Julius Lüning

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